

Multi-Aspect Dense Retrieval for Large JSON Files

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by

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Abstract

Multi-Aspect Dense Retrieval is an interesting field, where a bi-encoder architecture is used to encode queries and documents independently and calculate their similarity score based on a similarity function like cosine similarity. To compute the query and document encoding respectively, the output embeddings of a transformer encoder, like BERT, is used to extract aspect embedding and fuse them using a weighted sum.

The purpose of this paper is to analyze its applicability on large JSON files. Unfortunately, despite all the promising interim results, all models had a very poor performance. This shows the weaknesses of a too small dataset. Multiple design decisions around multi-aspect dense retrieval models, like a special loss to handle continuous aspect values and a chunk fusion network, are discussed.

This paper also presents some insights into the model architecture and its interpretability. before giving further ideas for improvements.

Keywords: Dense Retrieval, Embeddings, BERT, Chunking, Multi-Aspect

Abstract (in German)

Multi-Aspect Dense Retrieval ist ein spannendes Feld, in dem eine Bi-Encoder-Architektur verwendet wird, um Abfragen und Dokumente unabhängig voneinander zu kodieren und ihre Ähnlichkeitsbewertung auf der Grundlage einer Ähnlichkeitsfunktion wie der Cosinus-Ähnlichkeit zu berechnen. Um die Abfrage- bzw. Dokumentenkodierung zu berechnen, werden die Embeddings eines Transformator-Encoders wie z.B. BERT verwendet, um die Aspekt-Embeddings zu extrahieren und sie mit einer gewichteten Summe wieder zu vereinen.

In dieser Arbeit soll die Anwendbarkeit dieses Verfahrens auf große JSON-Dateien untersucht werden. Leider haben alle Modelle trotz der vielversprechenden Zwischenergebnisse eine sehr schlechte Leistung gezeigt. Dies zeigt die Schwächen eines zu kleinen Datensatzes. Es werden mehrere Design-Entscheidungen für Multi-Aspekt Dense Retrieval Modelle erörtert, wie z. B. ein spezieller Loss zur Behandlung kontinuierlicher Aspektwerte und ein Chunk-Fusion-Netzwerk.

Außerdem werden einige Einblicke in die Modellarchitektur und ihre Interpretierbarkeit gegeben, bevor weitere Ideen für Verbesserungen vorgestellt werden.

Schlagerwörter: Dense Retrieval, Embeddings, BERT, Chunking, Multi-Aspekt

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List of Abbreviations

AEN	
Aspect Extraction Network.....	12
AFN	
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AI	
Artificial Intelligence	1
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Multi-Aspect Dense Retrieval for Large JSON Files

1 Introduction

Fast and reliable search engines are a fundamental part of today's digital landscape. Information retrieval (IR) has become increasingly significant in providing users with relevant information quickly. Especially in an age of rapidly increasing data volume, velocity, and complexity, modern search engines should enable users to get relevant results with minimal effort, like a natural text query¹.

Particularly in document search with only a query text, where data might be unstructured or contain unstructured pieces of information, standard database queries fail to address this task. Even modern search engines, which rely on lexical-based representations as in keyword search, might fail to operate here due to the lack of profound text understanding. Semantic-based search, however, aims to solve this problem. By utilizing deep learning to create vector representations of queries and documents, also called embeddings, dense retrieval can calculate similarity scores between those embeddings in the vector space and retrieve matching query-document pairs by their meaning. This approach is further described by Zhan et al. in “Learning To Retrieve”.

A representative example of such an AI-powered search system, including answer generation for a great user experience, is Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG). This method harnesses dense retrieval to get relevant document passages, typically from a vector database, and passes them into a large language model (LLM) along with the query to generate a natural language answer (Lewis et al., 2020). Inspired by this technology and the given problem, the subject for this thesis was conceived.

1.1 Problem and Goal of this Work

Within Clausohm-Software GmbH, large amounts of car data are handled. In one state, there are so-called enriched cars, which are enriched with a good deal of different information from various data sources. One car is represented by a large multilingual JSON, which is considered a document. All car documents together form the document corpus. In the course of this work, a search engine for enriched cars is developed. The user should be able to enter a natural language query and is then provided with a list of length k ² with the most relevant documents from a given document corpus.

Since pure document retrieval is desired instead of question answering, there is no need for RAG. First, we require no answer generation, and second, it does not make much sense to retrieve document passages for this use case since they cannot represent the document as a whole. Calculating a document match score using retrieved passage scores might yield usable results, but it is likely to reveal some drawbacks regarding missing context. For that, it might seem promising to represent the whole document

¹ A natural language query is a search or data retrieval request formulated in human language, rather than a specialized query language. In this work, a query refers to a search request for cars.

² k is a manually set parameter for similarity search and is further described in section 3.5

using only a single vector. However, by using this approach, the embedding can become too generalized, even more so with an increasing document size, and might miss covering specific aspects of the document. This also applies for the query, since it easily becomes too large while searching for multiple aspects at once.

Recent research has brought up a new state-of-the-art ad-hoc document retriever that exactly covers those needs. Kong et al. propose a Multi-Aspect Dense Retrieval Model (MADRM), which will be explained in detail in Chapter 3. It also works with embeddings but pays attention to multiple aspects, like brand or color in the case of car data, of a document or query. The ability to extract aspect representations from text renders the technique the most promising. Therefore, the applicability of Multi-Aspect Dense Retrieval (MADR) as well as possible adjustments will be researched in this thesis. Adjustments come up through the requirements of this work and are further defined in Section 1.3.

1.2 Requirements

To come up with a useful result for the search engine, the following points have to be considered:

1. The car data is provided as JSON files. A car object has a complex structure with keys that might change a bit over time and an average size of 750 KB. It contains a mix of descriptive texts, categorized and semi-categorized texts, URLs, dates, and numbers (some including units while others do not). Semi-categorized means that it looks like categories exist while the values are maintained manually, which leads to slightly different values.
2. The document corpus approximately consists of 100,000 to 500,000 files, which sums up to around 75 to 375 GB of data. This must be considered for efficient similarity computation.
3. The data for this work is based on the German market, but all kinds of languages are possible. It is even possible for a single car object to contain multiple languages, as it might contain multiple translation texts. That is why multilingual support is essential for long-term use and should be considered.
4. An API to interact with the model should be provided, since running Python code manually can be cumbersome. This will be a lightweight Python backend containerized for easy and OS-independent deployment.
5. A user should get a response in a reasonable amount of time. That is meant for one user using the system simultaneously for one query at a time. Scalability is not part of this work. To define the term reasonable, the definitions from Doherty & Sorenson are used: an immediate response time of 300 ms to 1 sec would be desirable, but a transient response time of 1 to 5 sec is sufficient to keep the user engaged. So, the model should process within a maximum time span of 5 seconds.

These are the most important points to provide a Proof of Concept (POC) for a new, state-of-the-art retrieval model using MADR.

1.3 Research Objectives

To sum up, this work will cover the following research contribution:

1. Analyze the applicability of MADR for large and complex data provided as JSON files.
2. Introduce more than three aspects, like the ones presented in the paper by Kong et al., to cover the complexity of a car object.
3. Special treatment of dates and numbers in a MADRM to enhance comparison of numerical data.
4. Implement a chunking mechanism³ to cover large queries and particularly documents.
5. Explore the efficiency of similarity search with larger embeddings than 128 dimensional ones for more accurate retrieval.

1.4 Content Overview

The next chapter will explain the methodology. Chapter 3 will then place this work within the context of current research. It provides an overview of state-of-the-art technology and work related to this thesis. Aside from that, it explains the models used and aims to provide an understanding of the underlying technologies. Afterward, chapters 4, 5, and 6 are all about the data and its preparation, the model, and the training process. Chapter 7 will then present the results. Finally, chapter 8 will give some ideas on further research and future work on this subject before concluding in chapter 9.

1.5 Recap

By utilizing embeddings learned from deep neural networks, modern semantic-based search engines follow a superior approach compared to lexical-based search engines. They can understand the meaning of text and capture complex information, which enables more relevant search results.

This thesis captures a new state-of-the-art ad-hoc document retrieval method, Multi-Aspect Dense Retrieval, and its applicability for enriched car data used at Clausohm-Software GmbH. Further, potential valuable adjustments to this approach (e.g., chunking) are discussed and evaluated. Overall, the model should efficiently provide relevant search results while dealing with difficulties like large and complex documents and multilingualism.

³ Chunking divides input, which is too long to fit into the model, into multiple smaller parts, which are processed individually. To produce the final model output afterward, the separated chunk outputs have to be merged.

2 Methodology

This chapter provides a short overview of the steps taken and resources used for this work. It also targets special formatting and styles utilized to enhance the clarity of the presented information.

2.1 Research Design

The main objective of this paper is to implement a dense retrieval model. Therefore, a developmental and experimental research design was chosen. The model proposed by Kong et al. has been reimplemented since its code was not published. From this starting point, further customizations using suggestions from other papers (Bi et al., 2024; Sun et al., 2023, 2024) and findings from experiments have been made. This way, the deductive and inductive approaches complement each other by first testing already-made suggestions deductively and then inductively exploring further potential improvements.

To compare the models, different metrics are measured during training and evaluation on the treated dataset. This allows a quantitative analysis of the results and comparison between the models.

2.2 Materials and Instruments

For development, Jupyter notebooks were utilized in combination with a remote Jupyter server running inside a singularity container. The server was provided by the university and was equipped with an NVIDIA A100-PCIE-40GB GPU cluster, of which five were used to train the models. The singularity container uses `python:3.10-bookworm` as the base image from Docker Hub and has the necessary Python packages installed—`torch` and `transformers` were used to implement the model. PyTorch is a popular choice for research and was selected due to its simplicity. The package `wandb` is found to be very useful to report metrics and visualize training progress.

The developed code and model, as well as the dataset, belong to Clausohm-Software GmbH and will not be published.

2.3 Notations

Table 1 provides an overview of the notations used in this paper. This way, they must not be listed anew every time.

Table 1: A summary of notations used in this paper.

Notation	Description
q, d	The query or document in the retrieval task.
R	A result list.
A, a	A set of aspects. $A = \{a_i\}$, a particular aspect. $a \in A$
V	Vocabulary for all aspects. $V = \{V_a\}$
V_a	Vocabulary for a particular aspect a . $V_a \in V$ E.g., $V_{color} = \{red, green, blue\}$
H	Hidden size (768).
S	Sequence length (token count of input).
Φ_{BERT}	BERT’s last hidden state embeddings. $\Phi_{BERT} \in \mathbb{R}^{S \times H}$
Q, K, V	Query, key, and value vectors.
W^Q, W^K, W^V	Weights for Q, K, V projections. $W^Q, W^K, W^V \in \mathbb{R}^{H \times H}$
P^Q, P_C^Q	Free trainable parameter for query vector. P_C^Q is used for chunking. $P^Q \in \mathbb{R}^{ A \times H}, P_C^Q \in \mathbb{R}^{ A +1 \times 1 \times H}$
Ω^q, Ω^d	A set of aspect annotations for query or document. $\Omega = \{\Omega_{a_i}\}$
Ω_a^q, Ω_a^d	A set of category annotations of an aspect for query or document. $\Omega_a \in \Omega$ E.g., $\Omega_{color}^q = \{red\}$ for a query containing color red.
E_{CLS}, E_a	CLS token or aspect embedding. $E_{CLS}, E_a \in \mathbb{R}^H$
E_q, E_d	Final embedding of a query or document. $E_q, E_d \in \mathbb{R}^P$
C, c	A set of chunks. $C = \{c_i\}$, a particular chunk. $c \in C$
E_{AC}	All chunked aspect embeddings. $E_{AC} = \{E_{a_c}\}$
E_{a_c}	Aspect embedding for a particular chunk c . $E_{a_c} \in \mathbb{R}^H$
w_a, w_{a_c}	Aspect weight for aspect a or aspect weight for a particular chunk c .
x_c^a, y_c^a	Predictions and labels for category c of aspect a .
U_a	Aspect embedding table for aspect a . $U_a \in \mathbb{R}^{ V_a \times H}$
L_{MLM}, L_{AP}^a	MLM-Loss, Aspect Prediction Loss for aspect a .
Q_B, D_B	In-batch queries or documents.
REL	Relevance score matrix. $REL \in [-1, 1]^{ Q_B \times D_B }$

For simplicity, statements like $\forall a \in A$ as well as indices, such as a_i , are omitted in equations as intentions are clear and calculations are the same for each aspect, chunk, query, document, etc.

2.4 Depictions

Code

In this paper, code snippets, class names, and variable names are used to illustrate examples and to support better understanding. Code related text is marked using a monospaced font and looks like this:

```
# code example
```

Literal Quotes

Literal quotes also have their own style and are displayed the following way:

“This is a quote.” (Author)

Prompts

The prompts provided in Appendix B are also displayed using a specific prompt style, which looks like this:

This is a prompt.

2.5 Translations

Since the data is in German, some contents used for evaluation as well as the prompts in Appendix B are translated to English or possibly Spanish for demonstration purposes. To minimize personal bias, those texts are translated using DeepL.

3 Related Work and Preliminaries

This chapter explains the technologies used throughout this paper and presents studies related to the topics. First, the basics of dense retrieval and embeddings will be explained before continuing to transformers and, in particular, BERT. From there, MADR is shortly introduced, followed by long document treatment as well as ranking and similarity search.

3.1 Sparse and Dense Vector Representations

Vectors have a long history in information retrieval. They are being used to represent text in the vector space model (VSM). Each dimension in this space corresponds to a single term, word or phrase, from the whole vocabulary of a given corpus. So, each text is translated into a point in this vector space. This allows for the comparison and retrieval of similar texts, like similar documents to a given query, based on vector angles and lengths as well as distances between the points. Often, the cosine of the angle between two vectors is used as the numeric similarity, called Cosine Similarity. Singhal describes the VSM, its use, and key techniques like term weighting.

Traditional and still widely adopted information retrieval techniques use lexical-based search algorithms like Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) or BM25, which represent queries and documents as sparse vectors. Such non-neural retrievers were explained in detail by Robertson & Zaragoza. Sparse vectors represent text in a high-dimensional space, using one dimension for each term of the vocabulary. The values inside those vectors are weights, which are assigned to the terms based on their presence and frequency in a text. That leads to many zeros, as mostly only a few terms of the entire vocabulary are present, which yields the name of sparse vectors. Despite their size, they are computationally efficient because of their sparsity—many operations can skip the zero entries.

But in reality, documents most of the time do not just consist of one text but of multiple fields, like title, abstract, and body. Zamani et al. cover this topic and compare non-neural vs. neural multi-field retrievers. For a non-neural example, as an extension to BM25, Robertson & Zaragoza further proposed BM25F, where the F stands for fields. The idea is to combine term frequencies across fields on a per-term basis before computing a retrieval score using the balanced BM25. Zamani et al. suggest NRM-F as an approach that uses neural networks. The name NRM-F is inspired by BM25F and stands for a deep **n**eural **r**anking **m**odel for multi-field retrieval. It combines field-level embeddings of same-type fields, which are then again aggregated into a document embedding.

Embeddings are dense vectors with much fewer dimensions than sparse vectors, since a dimension does not represent a single term of the vocabulary. In return, each dimension is a continuous non-zero value. They capture not only the lexical, but also the semantic

meaning of text or other high-level properties, which makes them a powerful tool in natural language processing (NLP). While algorithms like BM25 might fail due to the use of different terms in queries and documents, also called the vocabulary mismatch problem, embeddings capture the meaning of text and are still as fast as traditional methods (Zhan et al., 2020). It might be worth pointing out that embeddings of similar words are located near each other in the vector space. They might also carry more complex relationships between words.

“For example, the result of a vector calculation $\text{vec}(\text{"Madrid"}) - \text{vec}(\text{"Spain"}) + \text{vec}(\text{"France"})$ is closer to $\text{vec}(\text{"Paris"})$ than to any other word vector.” (Mikolov et al., 2013)

Embedding vectors are learned by using deep neural networks (DNNs) and form the foundation of dense retrieval (DR). Dense retrieval is the term used to describe the retrieval of texts using their embeddings and then performing a similarity search. Zhan et al. give a good overview of the topic, including DR model architecture and ways to improve DR effectiveness and efficiency.

3.2 Transformers and BERT

Figure 1: The Transformer – model architecture (Vaswani et al., 2017).

To generate embeddings, different models can be used. BERT and BERT-based models are a popular choice for this because they have a bi-encoder architecture. BERT stands for **Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers** and was developed by

Devlin et al. As its name suggests, it is a transformer model, which means that it is only relying on attention mechanisms rather than recurrent or convolution layers (Vaswani et al., 2017). Other language representation models, such as the Generative Pre-trained Transformer (GPT) (Radford et al., 2018), use a unidirectional model architecture, which lets a token only see previous but not following tokens. This is good for generative models since the next token should be predicted for generation instead of used for context, but not for accurate language representations. Through the bidirectional structure, BERT can capture the context more reliably:

"Intuitively, it is reasonable to believe that a deep bidirectional model is strictly more powerful than either a left-to-right model or the shallow concatenation of a left-to-right and a right-to-left model." (Devlin et al., 2018)

It has a typical transformer architecture and is very similar to the work of Vaswani et al., which is shown in Figure 1. But BERT only uses the encoder site, which is now called a transformer block, and stacks it multiple times. In this paper, the BERT_{base} multilingual version of the model is used, which utilizes 12 stacked transformer blocks with 12 self-attention heads each. It uses a hidden size (H) (dimensionality of embeddings) of 768 and has 179 million parameters in total. An overview of the BERT model with additional component markers and annotations is shown in Figure 2, where colors are based on the ones used in Figure 1. The following subsections dive into each part of BERT in more depth.

Figure 2: BERT model architecture printed using PyTorch with additional annotations.

3.2.1 Input/Output

As shown in Figure 1, input embeddings are needed. Those embeddings are token-wise sums of learned token embeddings, segment embeddings, and position embeddings. This is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: BERT Input Embeddings Calculation (Devlin et al., 2018).

A token is a reoccurring set of characters that thereby most often represent a word or syllable. A model requires a fixed vocabulary, which means a fixed number of tokens, to learn token embeddings. That is why words are usually broken down into the root form as well as prefixes and suffixes to keep the vocabulary size small and enable a consistent understanding of words. In BERT, tokens belonging to the previous token are marked with ##.

There are also two special tokens added to the input: [CLS] and [SEP], which are shown in Figure 3. The CLS token (short for Classifier Token) captures the context of the input and therefore can be used for classification tasks on the sentence. It is always the first token of the input. The SEP token stands for Separator Token and separates two segments for some NLP tasks like Next Sentence Prediction, which use different segment embeddings for the tokens of segments A and B, respectively. It is always the last token, and if two segments are used, it also occurs between those segments. This work does not capture segments, so only one SEP token is present in the inputs as the last token to attend to.

As output, BERT provides embeddings for each input token in the sequence (including CLS and SEP), which means that the output is a matrix of shape $S \times H$, where S is the sequence length.

3.2.2 Transformer Encoder Block

To compute the output embeddings, the input embeddings pass through several transformer encoder blocks. As visualized in Figure 1, inputs first pass a multi-head self-attention layer and are then summed to the attention input—this is also called residual connection (He et al., 2016)—as well as layer normalized.

Self-attention is used to give every token a weight in the context of a given sentence. As often in AI-research, attention tries to mimic human attention. It works by assigning

scores to the input values and computing a weighted sum. This way, the model distinguishes between what is more important and what is less important. This is done by matrix multiplication, which is the dot-product, of a query vector (Q) and a key vector (K) to compute the scores and apply them to the value vector (V). The underlying attention mechanisms for BERT are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Scaled Dot-Product and Multi-Head Attention (Vaswani et al., 2017).

The basis is a Scaled Dot-Product attention, which adds scaling and optional score masking to the default attention mechanism described above. The scaling is added to counteract extremely small gradients while model training, which might occur with higher dimensionality and therefore larger dot-product magnitudes. Scaled Dot-Product Attention is again used in Multi-Head Attention, which is the chosen mechanism in BERT. Multi-Head Attention linearly projects the Q, K, and V vectors into multiple attention heads (12 for BERT_{base}), concatenates them, and again projects to compute the result.

“Multi-head attention allows the model to jointly attend to information from different representation subspaces at different positions. With a single attention head, averaging inhibits this.” (Vaswani et al., 2017)

In the case of self-attention, which is used in BERT, key, value, and query inputs are all derived from the same source. This allows each token to interact with every other token to determine its importance in the given context.

After the attention layer, there is a feed-forward layer in the encoder block, which means that the data is processed straightforwardly from input to output direction without looping back. It is essentially a dense layer, which adds complexity and depth to the model and provides non-linearity. While attention layers help the model focus on essential parts of the input data and incorporate context, feed-forward layers allow it to transform these focused features into something more useful.

3.3 Multi-Aspect Dense Retrieval

Multi-Aspect Dense Retrieval was first introduced by Kong et al. (2022) and is still quite unexplored. They propose to use an Aspect Extraction Network (AEN) and Aspect Fusion Network (AFN) instead of the last transformer block in BERT. The AEN is a Scaled Dot-Product Attention layer to extract aspect embeddings from the BERT output. This way, each aspect is represented by one embedding. Those embeddings may be learned during Aspect Learning (AL), where they are passed into a classification task to predict the aspect vocabulary. For this task, each aspect a has a given vocabulary V_a . E.g., the aspect *color* might have the classes $V_{color} = \{red, green, blue\}$ while the aspect *fuel type* may have the values

$$V_{fuel_type} = \{electrical, hybrid, petrol, diesel, gas\}.$$

In addition to the given aspects, they also use one more ‘‘OTHER’’ aspect to capture information not covered by the other aspects. After aspect extraction, aspect embeddings are fused in the AFN using suggested methods, like Presence Weighting or CLS-Gating, to obtain a final embedding. MADRM enables the computation of document embeddings offline. This way, similarity search is more efficient during inference. It might be worth mentioning that query and document encoders do not share the same models and are trained independently.

Figure 5: MADRM (Kong et al., 2022).

Some papers refer to the MADR approach and provide suggestions to further improve it. Sun et al. (2023) argue that predicting classes while aspect learning is not enough to capture relations between them. For example, among the category values, ‘‘Hunting & Fishing’’ is more related to ‘‘Sports & Outdoors’’ while unrelated to ‘‘Pet Supplies’’ (Sun et al., 2023). They propose to pre-train BERT by using the segments with aspect text (the values of the aspect vocabulary V_a) and query or document text to conduct mutual prediction. They insert special tokens for each aspect, which are learned while aspect-learning and form the aspect embeddings.

In 2024, Sun et al. further investigated the subject and came up with a similar solution. In the new approach, they only insert special aspect and granularity tokens before the actual input tokens, without using aspect vocabulary. They introduce different granularity levels for all aspects to capture both coarse and fine-grained semantic relations between aspect values.

Since the code of MADRM was not published, Bi et al. (2024) cover the reproducibility of its results and compare the model with other models on a public dataset. They could not reproduce its effectiveness, but they provide enhancements like using the CLS token embedding instead of learning the “OTHER” aspect or making use of the first k -tokens⁴ of the BERT output as aspect embeddings as an alternative to utilizing an additional attention head. This way, the authors were able to achieve promising results with best MADR performance on the MA-Amazon dataset.

3.4 Long Transformer Inputs

It must be considered that documents are quite long, and transformers, which use full-attention, have a limited input length in terms of quadratic growing memory use with growing input length. In particular, BERT, which is the base transformer encoder used in this work, has a maximum input size of 512 tokens. There are several solutions that address this type of problem; the simplest one of all is truncating the input. This is still widely used and is also applied with an even smaller input size in MADR (Kong et al., 2022). But there are other techniques that show state-of-the-art performance on long inputs for transformers.

For example, there is the Longformer (Beltagy et al., 2020). It is a transformer model that uses different attention windows than the full-attention one. This way, the attention matrix does not grow quadratic but grows linearly with the input length. The authors present different patterns for different use cases.

Figure 6: Different attention patterns (Beltagy et al., 2020).

Another approach that achieves comparable results to Longformer, is to combine BERT with a LSTM or CNN (Khandve et al., 2022). The input is divided into chunks, which are passed to BERT. The resulting embeddings are then passed through a LSTM or CNN. With the help of max pooling as well as a classification layer, the outputs are used for classification tasks.

⁴ k refers to the number of aspects.

A model that uses a similar idea to BERT + LSTM is CogLTX (Ding et al., 2020). It mimics the human process of remembering information in text and uses a process called “MemRecall”. The long document is divided into multiple chunks, called blocks in their paper, and relevant information is extracted from them concerning a given query. Already “remembered” information is also considered during MemRecall and eventually forgotten. This way, only a few relevant details are kept from a long document.

Considering the aspect extraction use case in this paper, the Longformer is a promising approach because it enhances the base encoder without the need for further adjustments for long inputs. Nevertheless, BERT is the preferred model to establish the POC since it was already used for MADRAL and does not have to be learned from scratch. Approaches like MemRecall are not suitable for this task, as documents should be processed independently without a query. This enables offline computation of document embeddings and speeds up inference.

Inspired by BERT + LSTM and techniques like attention (3.2.2) and CLS-Gating (5.4), this paper presents another chunking approach in section 5.5. It extracts aspect embeddings for each chunk before merging them to a single set of aspect embeddings.

3.5 Text Ranking and Similarity Search

To fulfill the main task of a search engine, namely document retrieval, a fast, and reliable search method must be applied. Figure 7 shows different techniques to compute similarity scores between a query and a document. ColBERT (Khattab & Zaharia, 2020) uses late-interaction, which means that document embeddings are computed offline and then interact in a minimal computation with the query embeddings.

Figure 7: Different query-document matching paradigms (Khattab & Zaharia, 2020).

Dense embeddings, especially high-dimensional ones, make it harder and more resource-intensive to compute the nearest neighbors, in particular on a large document corpus. The larger the corpus, the less usable ColBERT is because every document has to interact with the query to compute their similarity.

Another paper examines the widely diversified field of text ranking with embeddings and transformers (Lin et al., 2020). It explains how to use different model architectures, among them the bi-encoder architecture used for MADR, and how to train them for text ranking. In contrast to interaction-based similarity, the bi-encoder architecture used in

this paper follows representation-based similarity, where queries and documents are represented as embeddings independently, and a simple similarity function like dot-product or cosine similarity is used to calculate their similarities. This enables the use of the maximum inner product search (MIPS) problem for retrieval.

One widely studied solution to this problem is the approximate nearest neighbor (ANN) search. With ANN, not every vector in the dataset has to be compared with the query vector, but only approximately the best ones. It aims to quickly find the best points in a (document) dataset close to a given query point. The gain in speed is a trade-off for accuracy.

The method used in this work for efficient vector similarity search at scale is ScaNN (Guo et al., 2020). ScaNN stands for **Scalable Nearest Neighbors**. It uses anisotropic vector quantization together with a search tree to largely gain MIPS performance. It is also used in MADR. Techniques like quantization and partitioning were researched in detail in other important papers regarding ANN (Andoni et al., 2018).

3.6 Evaluation Metrics

To evaluate the training and retrieval results of the model, some measurable metrics are needed. This section explains the metrics used in this paper. Other works have already examined how to evaluate search engines (Sirotkin, 2013) and dense text ranking models (Lin et al., 2020).

The most common metrics to evaluate classification tasks are precision (P) and recall (R) because they are easy to interpret. Precision is the portion of true positive classified items of all positive classified items. Recall, however, is the portion of true positives of all positive items in the dataset or batch.

$$P = \frac{\text{true positives}}{\text{true positives} + \text{false positives}} = \frac{\text{relevant retrieved results}}{\text{overall retrieved results}} \quad (1)$$

$$R = \frac{\text{true positives}}{\text{true positives} + \text{false negatives}} = \frac{\text{relevant retrieved results}}{\text{relevant items in dataset}} \quad (2)$$

The F_1 -score represents a harmonic mean of these two metrics, providing a balance of both. This helps to assess both performances at once.

$$F_1 = 2 \frac{PR}{P + R} \quad (3)$$

There are many metrics for the evaluation of ranking tasks. However, previous work has shown that the **normalized discounted cumulative gain** (NDCG) performs best for the user experience (Sirotkin, 2013, P. 116) and is able to represent the quality of results best.

“Rather, the relevant question tends to be whether one result list has a higher quality than another. It can be asked to compare different search engines; or to see whether a new algorithm actually improves the user experience; or to compare a new development with a baseline. The common feature is the comparison of the quality of two result lists.” (Sirotkin, 2013, P. 57)

While precision treats all results equally, it does not take into account the decreasing user attention associated with a growing result rank. NDCG solved this issue by discounting the retrieved document score by a discount function, usually \log_2 . This way, all scores from the third rank are discounted and weighted less for the DCG. The normalization takes the best possible DCG result of the labels and uses it as denominator of the result list DCG. This way, the NDCG is always in the interval $[0, 1]$.

$$DCG(R, q) = \sum_{(i,d) \in R} \frac{2^{rel(q,d)} - 1}{\log_2(i + 1)} \quad (4)$$

$$NDCG(R, q) = \frac{DCG(R, q)}{DCG(R_{best}, q)} \quad (5)$$

These are the four metrics used during this work. For ranking, they are typically used with a cutoff after a given number of results to mimic a search result list. This is denoted with a *@Cutoff* notation behind the metric. For example, $P@10$ is the precision of the first ten elements of the result list.

3.7 Recap

This chapter went over the underlying technologies used in this work, as well as related papers. It covered sparse and dense vector representations, where dense vector representations for text are also called embeddings. The transformer architecture, together with the BERT model, was explained in detail before proceeding to MADR. MADR uses BERT embeddings for aspect extraction and fuses them to obtain a single embedding for a query or document. The challenge of long document inputs was also discussed. Lastly, a short introduction to text ranking and similarity search, as well as evaluation metrics, was given.

4 The Dataset

To train the models and evaluate their effectiveness, queries, documents, and relevance scores are needed. The dataset used is completely based on a set of documents. Each document contains the JSON of an enriched car and was retrieved from a company-internal database. Files have a size of approximately 750 KB and include much different information about cars.

The data in documents is structured into multiple parts of information, which also partly mesh. Take, for example, the parts "attributes", "technical", and "equipment". Attributes may also refer to equipment, and vice versa. Each part contains keys for different aspects of a car. An aspect is considered any information about a car and its data. The values of aspect keys are nested objects or arrays of object, which are partially nested. While those objects might further contain nested layers, at the leaves they may include, for example, origin⁵, value, unit, and text for multiple languages.

For the simplicity of the POC, only cars from the German market were chosen. Due to capacity reasons, approximately only 250 documents from each market, like new cars, used cars, etc., are used, which makes up 1,926 documents. This is now considered the document corpus used to train the model instead of all documents available. This selection of documents had to be carefully analyzed to create meaningful aspects and vocabulary.

4.1 Aspects and Vocabulary

This section dives into the extraction of aspects from documents and the creation of the associated vocabulary. It explains the preprocessing procedure for aspect extraction and how the resulting vocabulary is structured.

4.1.1 Preprocessing

For easier analysis and data extraction, the documents are flattened and iteratively simplified during dataset preparation. This means that all keys on a path to a leave-value are merged into a new key. That is similar to the JSON path, but since it should represent an aspect name, it uses a dash instead of a point as a delimiter. This way, flattened documents only contain one level of merged keys, which represent an aspect name, and the associated value. Values are of primitive types or an array of primitive types.

Since the data also contains arrays of objects, they are indexed using primary keys and converted to objects before flattening, if possible. Otherwise, indexes were used as keys. To further simplify the data, some keys are shortened, some are merged when they refer to the same aspect, while some values need special treatment, like loading JSON strings or splitting lists separated by a delimiter. This leads to some aspect values being

⁵ Origin means the origin of the information while the enrichment process.

arrays of multiple primitive values. Furthermore, if an aspect is considered categorical, then a key is used to represent its values. Since most of those aspects have some type of key present in the document, this can be used. Otherwise, the value itself is used as a key.

Additionally, metadata, for example, the market type extracted from the filename, is added to the flattened document. In the last step of preprocessing, special characters and different encodings are cleaned.

Note that all the preprocessing described above is done only for aspect and vocabulary extraction and is not used at any other point within the training process.

4.1.2 Aspects

Since not all information in a document is useful to search for cars, a list of the most important aspects is extracted from the document keys. In total, 241 aspects have been selected, of which 119 are categorical, 102 are numerical, and 20 are dates and times. The selection is based on a manual evaluation of possible aspect importance. For more aspects, more analysis has to be done to find duplicate fields with different keys or other necessary preprocessing steps. For this reason, for some less popular aspects, it was decided to omit them from the POC.

Table 2: Examples of used and unused aspects

Categorical	Numerical	Dates and times	Unused
color_out	max_output	model_year	...-origin
carline	mileage_total	production_date	...-language
fuel_type	top_speed	warranties-asg-dateexpiry	trim_line-url-img_big

4.1.3 Vocabulary

For query generation and aspect learning, a vocabulary is needed for the aspects to have categories. In this work, the vocabulary is extended by category words, such that each aspect has a set of categories and each category has a set of words. Those words are used for query generation, as described in section 4.3. If some aspects contain arrays of values, all are added as words to the vocabulary. For numerical and datetime values, there are no words, and the values directly represent the categories. However, for technical and flexibility reasons, there is just one category with all possible values as words in the implementation. For example, if a query uses a span for a numerical aspect, all values matching the span are annotated. Following the relevance calculation in 4.4, a document creates a match if it also annotates a value from the span. If categories for each numerical value were used, this would not be possible.

Examples of one categorical and one numerical aspect of the vocabulary are presented in Figure 8. The first has categories and associated words using IDs as keys, and the second one has a placeholder category with numerical values.

```
1  "carline": {
2      "51900": [
3          "51900",
4          "Audi e-tron",
5          "e-tron",
6          "e-tron"
7      ],
8      ...
9  },
10 "max_output": {
11     "": [
12         "85 kw",
13         "347 PS",
14         ...
15     ]
16 }
```

Figure 8: Example aspects vocabulary.

4.2 Document Labels

With the vocabulary in hand, the document labeling process is straightforward. Since there are already flattened documents, the following steps can be applied:

1. Filter aspect keys by those in the aspect list from 4.1.2.
2. For numerical and datetime aspects, directly annotate the value(s). For categorical aspects, annotate the key.
3. For categorical aspects, use terms from the annotated category to annotate similar categories. This has to be done if, for example, a document annotated with the carline “Audi Q5 Sportback”, then also the broader category “Audi Q5” should be annotated.

The result is a dictionary of aspect keys and a list of category annotations for categorical aspects and numerical values for continuous⁶ aspects.

4.3 Query Generation

As there is no dataset for car search queries with annotated aspects and because of the lack of resources to collect one within the timespan of this work, a query dataset is generated. Queries are generated using three different methods:

⁶ Continuous aspects refer to both, numerical and datetime aspects.

1. A query is based on one document and uses its annotations.
2. A query is created with random annotations from the whole vocabulary.
3. A query is generated using a template provided by ChatGPT 4 while also using the entire vocabulary.

4.3.1 Document-based Queries

For document-based queries, aspect groups are defined. Aspect groups are collections of aspects related to each other, like all aspects of consumption or a warranty. For example, warranty type, start, end, etc. form a group. For those groups, templates with natural text are defined. The way templates function is further defined in Appendix A.

To generate a query, random aspect groups are selected, and group representations are generated using a self-made template engine with terms from a document. Furthermore, the group representations are shuffled and concatenated to obtain the final query. Each query is an exact match for the document used to create it.

4.3.2 Corpus-based Queries

A similar procedure is used to generate the queries, which use the entire vocabulary. The only difference is that there are no aspect groups but more detailed templates for all aspects, and aspects are directly picked on a random basis. Also, all categories and terms can be used here. This also makes room for queries that have no possible match.

4.3.3 GPT-generated Query Templates

ChatGPT 4 generated around 150 queries. It respected different target groups and query complexities. The prompts used for generation are provided in Appendix B. The resulting queries were manually transformed into templates for query generation. This might be helpful to enhance the dataset with more natural language and common search patterns. However, ChatGPT only used a handful of aspects. As a result, queries that were generated using the GPT templates do not represent the dataset sufficiently.

4.3.4 Query Dataset

Putting it all together, the query dataset a) contains exact matches for documents due to document-based queries, b) consists of enough randomized, and thus balanced, data from the whole vocabulary to properly represent the dataset, and c) is enriched with natural language queries that were generated using ChatGPT. Inspired by the train-validate-test split approach for datasets, 28,640 (20%) document-based, 100,240 (70%) vocabulary-based, and 14,320 (10%) GPT-based queries were generated. That sums up to 143,200 queries in total. The same distribution is applied to randomly split query and document datasets into train, validate, and test subsets.

Looking at the size of queries, the smallest one is tokenized with just 3 tokens, including CLS and SEP. This means it is only one word. The mean size of queries is 140 tokens, while the median lies at 79 tokens. The longest query consists of 1,176 tokens.

Hence, most of the queries, to be exact, 94.04%, fit into BERT’s token limit of 512 tokens.

Queries are already labeled during generation with the terms used to replace placeholders. If a term refers to multiple categories, all of them are annotated. As with the documents, broader categories, which include annotated and more specific ones, are added to the labels too.

4.4 Fine-tuning and Retrieval

The fine-tuning as well as the retrieval process additionally need relevance scores to evaluate the retrieved document scores. Since the labels are very precise, the relevance scores can be calculated. This is done by dividing the amount of the query aspects with at least one match with the document of a query-document pair by the total count of annotated aspects of the query:

$$rel(q, d) = \frac{1}{|\Omega^q|} \sum_{a \in A} \min(|\Omega_a^q \cap \Omega_a^d|, 1) \quad (6)$$

Using the equation above, retrieval scores for every query-document pair are calculated. To create the fine-tuning dataset, two more things have to be considered:

1. Train, validation, and test queries and documents should not be used differently while fine-tuning.
2. Pairing every query with each document results in

$$143,200 \text{ queries} \cdot 1,926 \text{ documents} = 275,803,200 \text{ possible pairs},$$

which is too much data to train on.

To deal with those issues, each query in the query training set is paired with the best-matching document in the document training set. It is done analogously for validation and test sets. Now, the fine-tune dataset only consists of as many elements as the query dataset. However, it only includes the best matching query-document pairs. Due to the calculation of the retrieval loss described in section 6.4, this should be sufficient since random in-batch query-document pairs are evaluated too.

4.5 Document Compression

Documents can be very long, which makes it impossible to fit them into a model like BERT with a limited input size of 512 tokens. The largest document in the corpus has a size of 699,002 tokens. Thus, it is reasonable to believe that 512 tokens cannot represent such a large document in any way. To counteract this, documents are compressed, which means that unnecessary parts are removed. Since neither origin nor language as-

pects are used, they, as well as URLs, are removed from the documents. Additionally, nested “value” objects⁷ that only contain one value are flattened.

These are the only preprocessing steps taken for documents used for retrieval because document structure might slightly change over time and thus should be mostly assumed as a black box. In 7.2.2, it was investigated whether breaking up the JSON structure might shrink the document size while preserving the model’s performance. However, this is not the case.

By applying these steps, the largest document now has a token size of 18,907, while the minimum is 2,084 tokens and the mean is 11,207 tokens. The median lies at 11,178 tokens, and 90% of the documents are under 13,997 tokens long. This is still too much to fit into BERT, but it is more representative than before. Furthermore, section 5.5 provides a possible solution for the limited input size.

Because documents are much larger than queries, it is okay to have fewer of them because the number of tokens is balanced when using chunking (5.5). While queries have around

$$100,000 \text{ training queries} \cdot 140 \frac{\text{mean tokens}}{\text{query}} = 14,000,000 \text{ tokens},$$

documents have approximately

$$1350 \text{ training documents} \cdot 11,200 \frac{\text{mean tokens}}{\text{documents}} = 15,120,000 \text{ tokens}.$$

When no chunking is used, this leads to problems described in Appendix D.

4.6 Recap

This chapter described the query, document, and fine-tuning datasets and explained how they are created. A smaller document corpus is selected from all the documents available. By flattening them and merging similar information, meaningful aspects and vocabulary are extracted for query generation. Queries are generated using templates and filled with terms from a) a specific document or b) the whole vocabulary. Additionally, templates provided by ChatGPT are used. The fine-tuning dataset contains relevance scores for every query-document pair, and the best query-document matches in each set of the training, validation, and test sets are used for training, validation, and testing, respectively. To make documents easier to process for models, they are preprocessed beforehand to make them smaller.

⁷ “value” object refers to an object associated with the key “value” inside the JSON structure.

5 Multi-Aspect Dense Retrieval Model

The original MADRM takes two networks, AEN and AFN, and uses them instead of the last transformer block in BERT.

“In fact, the AEN and AFN are analogous to the Multi-Head Self Attention (MHSA) and feedforward network (FFNN) in transformers, respectively.” (Kong et al., 2022)

Additionally, MADRAL further guides the model to produce proper aspect embeddings using Aspect Learning. This chapter describes each component of the MADRM in more detail and provides extensions as well as improvement suggestions.

5.1 BERT

BERT is the basis of all models trained in the course of this work. It is initialized using Google's public pretrained checkpoint “bert-base-multilingual-uncased”. The multilingual model was selected regarding multilingualism support and is only available as the base version of BERT. Uncased is used because it is common for search engines to make queries case-insensitive (*How to Search on Google - Google Search Help*, n.d.). This also makes it easier for the user since one does not have to check for cases, especially in German.

5.2 Aspect Extraction Network

The aspect extraction network uses the BERT output to extract aspect embeddings by utilizing a scaled dot-product attention layer. The BERT embeddings are projected through two separate linear layers W^K and W^V to obtain the K and V vectors with $K, V \in \mathbb{R}^{S \times H}$. The query vector Q, with $Q \in \mathbb{R}^{|A| \times H}$, is generated using a free, trainable parameter P^Q , which is also passed through a projection layer W^Q . Afterward, attention scores are calculated by the matrix multiplication of Q and K divided by the square root of the hidden size H . With the help of softmax, these scores are turned into aspect probabilities for each token.

Note that the CLS token is masked before the application of softmax because it captures contextual information and thus cannot be assigned to an aspect. This is done by assigning $1e-9$ to the CLS token logits. Aspect probabilities over input tokens is further investigated in section 0.

In the training process, a dropout is applied to the probabilities to prevent overfitting and help the model generalize better. In the last step of the AEN, the matrix multiplication of token-wise aspect probabilities and V generates the aspect embeddings.

$$E_a = \text{Attention}(P^Q W^Q, \Phi_{\text{BERT}} W^K, \Phi_{\text{BERT}} W^V) \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Attention}(Q, K, V) = \text{softmax}\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{H}}\right)V \quad (8)$$

Other papers suggest either using the top-k first embeddings of the BERT output as aspect embeddings (Bi et al., 2024) or adding new special tokens for aspects and/or granularity levels (Sun et al., 2024). This way, no aspect embeddings must be learned using attention, which can be a challenging process. While both might be a meaningful approach when having only a few aspects, they become impractical with more. Since this work is especially focused on large documents with many aspects, these ideas are omitted for the following reasons:

1. With more than 511 aspects, it is also not possible to use the top-k tokens anymore because that is the maximum BERT output size besides the CLS token.
2. By adding special aspect tokens for a growing number of aspects, the remaining token count for text input shrinks.
3. Granularity is not researched in this paper.

For the POC, only 241 aspects are used, but more aspects are conceivable.

In the original MADRAL, there is also an “OTHER” aspect, that captures information not covered by labeled aspects. Since it has no annotations and thus cannot be learned, its training totally relies on fine-tuning. Instead of using the “OTHER” aspect, the model could also use the CLS token embedding (E_{CLS}) in its place (Bi et al., 2024). In this paper, this model is called MADRAL-CLS.

5.3 Aspect Prediction Network

5.3.1 Original

The aspect prediction network (APN) is optional and used for aspect learning. With aspect learning, the model learns the aspect embeddings described above, except for the “OTHER” aspect. Without it, aspect embeddings would only represent latent aspects without meaning. During fine-tuning, the model would learn to utilize those aspects. That happens with any contextual information the model finds useful, which does not necessarily have to represent the chosen aspects.

It works by adding a classification layer for each aspect on top of the AEN. Those classification layers are used to predict the aspect vocabulary or aspect categories. Each layer takes one aspect embedding as input and outputs the probabilities for the associated aspect categories, i.e., $\text{Linear}(E_a) \in \mathbb{R}^{|V_a|}$. Analogous to the AEN, a dropout is applied to the scores before activation during training. In evaluation or production, the APN is not used since it only guides aspect learning. This makes the model more efficient during inference.

The weights of the classification layers can be seen as aspect embedding tables U_a , since they have the shape $|V_a| \times H$ for an aspect a . These tables can capture the meaning of aspect vocabulary and thus represent semantic relations between aspect categories. Examples regarding vocabulary embeddings are shown in 0. The classification works by using the dot-product similarity together with a sigmoid function to predict embedding similarities and hence category annotations. If no category of an aspect is annotated, the model learns an embedding, which has a low similarity score with each category embedding from U_a . This “none-embedding” is not present in the tables.

Note that the APN is shared between the query and the document encoder. It was tested with two individual APNs by accident. That works, but makes pre-training rather useless because aspect embeddings are trained very differently for the two encoders. Thus, they do not form a good foundation for fine-tuning and have to be matched during that training phase. They still do not necessarily have similar aspect embedding tables afterward. This reduces the interpretability of the model as well. A shared APN also enables parallel pre-training of the two encoders, or rather, it even requires it. Experiments (7.2.3) show that the model with a shared APN perform better than with an unshared one. By sharing the APN, the aspect embeddings are equal for both, queries and documents, which syncs the pre-training objective of the query and the document encoder and provides a good starting point for fine-tuning.

5.3.2 Continuous Values

Studies have shown that NLP models, especially BERT, have trouble with numbers (Wallace et al., 2019). They fail to capture numeration and magnitude, not to mention numerical operations like addition, sufficiently (Sundararaman et al., 2020). Numeration ability to represent associate numbers with their corresponding word representation, e.g., 3 = three, and magnitude is the actual value of the number.

This inspired the idea of predicting annotated intervals using the aspect embeddings. For all continuous aspects, the classification layer is replaced by a linear layer to predict the min and max values of the interval, i.e., $Linear(E_a) \in \mathbb{R}^2$. In this case, the weights of the layers can be seen as two individual embeddings for the maximum value. The higher the similarity score between them and the aspect embedding, the higher the predicted values, where 1 represents the maximum and 0 the minimum of the entire vocabulary. The two similarities create the predicted interval. While it is conceivable that a query might contain multiple values and not necessarily only one or an interval for a continuous aspect, this is rather unusual for the car domain. For example, you want cars with an exact price, minimum range, maximum consumption, or a length between two values. Using multiple different values for those aspects is quite uncommon.

The adjustment for continuous values is marked with an “N” behind the model’s abbreviation for “with numerical treatment”. Further improvements regarding numerical values are discussed in chapter 8 and not researched during this work.

5.3.3 Loss Adjustment

In contrast to the original MADRAL, sigmoid is used instead of softmax to calculate the predicted category probabilities here because it is usually the case that an aspect has multiple annotations. Thus, softmax would not fit this use case, as it transforms scores into a probability distribution. Accordingly, this APN uses binary cross-entropy instead of softmax cross-entropy as a loss function. This way, the model also indirectly learns aspect presence, since all labels for an aspect are 0 when there are no annotations, and thus the aspect is not present in the input.

$$L_{AP}^a = -\frac{1}{|V_a|} \sum_{c \in V_a} y_c^a \log x_c^a + (1 - y_c^a) \log(1 - x_c^a) \quad (9)$$

$$y_c^a = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } c \in \Omega_a \\ 0, & \text{else} \end{cases}, \quad x_c^a = \text{Linear}(E_a)_c$$

When the model with special treatment for continuous values is used, the mean squared error (MSE) loss is used for them as it is a regression problem. This applies only if the aspect is present in the labels, otherwise $L_{AP}^a = 0$.

$$L_{AP}^a = \frac{(x_{min}^a - y_{min}^a)^2 + (x_{max}^a - y_{max}^a)^2}{2} \quad (10)$$

$$y_{min}^a = \min(\Omega_a), \quad y_{max}^a = \max(\Omega_a)$$

$$x_{min}^a = \text{Linear}(E_a)_0, \quad x_{max}^a = \text{Linear}(E_a)_1$$

5.4 Aspect Fusion Network

To efficiently carry out ANN search, the aspect embeddings from the AEN are merged into a single embedding with a dimensionality of the hidden size representing the query or document. Kong et al. present three different approaches to it.

5.4.1 Weighted Sum

Weighted Sum learns a weight for each aspect, applies softmax over all of them, and computes the weighted sum of the aspect embeddings. The presence of an aspect in the input is not being considered here, which makes this method inferior to the others.

$$E_q = \sum_{a \in A} w_a \cdot E_a, \quad w_a = \frac{e^{\gamma_a}}{\sum_{a' \in A} e^{\gamma_{a'}}} \quad (11)$$

5.4.2 Presence Weighting

Presence Weighting is similar to Weighted Sum but takes into account whether an aspect is present in the input or not. The weight of an aspect is calculated by multiplying its probability of presence with the trainable importance parameter γ_a .

$$w_a(q) = P_a(q) \cdot \gamma_a \quad (12)$$

5.4.3 CLS-Gating

CLS-Gating utilized the Mixture of Experts (MoE) (Jacobs et al., 1991) approach to gate aspect embeddings based on the E_{CLS} . This way, the resulting representation is directly dependent on the BERT output, which makes this method more efficient (Kong et al., 2022). Also MURAL (Sun et al., 2024) uses CLS-Gating. Because of the promising results, this paper follows this approach too.

The E_{CLS} is passed through a linear layer to compute the logits for each aspect, i.e., $Linear(E_{CLS}) \in \mathbb{R}^{|A|}$. These logits are then softmaxed to obtain the aspect weights for the weighted sum.

$$w_a = \frac{e^{Linear(E_{CLS})_a}}{\sum_{a \in A} e^{Linear(E_{CLS})_a}} \quad (13)$$

As usual, a dropout is applied to the weights. This is done before using softmax for CLS-Gating.

Note that the AFN, except for presence weighting, is not used during pre-training, since the final embedding is not learned during that stage. Presence weighting already learns the aspect presence probability during pre-training and thus can be used there.

Following other papers (Kong et al., 2022; Sun et al., 2024), models are only trained using CLS-Gating.

5.5 Chunk Fusion Network

BERT can only process 512 tokens at once. Especially since the documents are much longer than that, a chunking mechanism is examined in this work. It is inspired by previous work done on large document ranking (Lin et al., 2020, P. 53). BERT inputs are chunked during preprocessing, which is further described in section 6.2, into blocks of 512 tokens. The following discussion will only target aspect merging, since it is analogous to the merging of CLS token embeddings, which are treated just as aspect embeddings. Merging CLS tokens embeddings is important to obtain an E_{CLS} to use for CLS-Gating.

The idea is to extract the aspect embeddings from each chunk and then merge all aspect embeddings related to the same aspect into one. The same is done for all CLS embeddings.

$$E_a = \sum_{c \in C_a} w_{a_c} \cdot E_{a_c} \quad (14)$$

This is possible because each aspect is only present once in a document. As a result, the task of the chunk fusion network (CFN) is to predict which chunk contains information relating to an aspect and “pick” the correct one.

For this type of problem, a softmax cross-entropy loss would be used. Unfortunately, there are no labels for aspects per chunk, and it is also unrealistic to have them in real-world data. That is why there is no extra loss for this network.

When thinking of queries, there might be multiple references to one aspect in a query, but since this is rarely the case over multiple chunks and most of the queries fit into the model at once, this is considered insignificant. Although it is possible to apply chunking to queries, it will probably be unfeasible in most cases. Because, on the one hand, queries are short enough most of the time⁸, and on the other hand, the time complexity for training as well as inference increases a lot when chunking is applied. For documents, time complexity does not affect inference because they are encoded offline first, but queries must be encoded on demand. That makes chunking feasible for documents but unfavorable for queries.

The presented approach differs from the BERT + LSTM/CNN one (Khandve et al., 2022) because no embeddings have to be merged, and no context has to be remembered. It would need to be used before the aspect extraction to create an embedding for the whole document to extract aspect embeddings. While this is imaginable, the JSON documents provided for this work can be reliably evaluated in chunks. That is why it is assumed that no long-distance attention is needed. Therefore, the aspect extraction is directly done on the chunk embedding to get more reliable aspect embeddings to pick from.

For the implementation, four different networks were tested.

5.5.1 No Chunking

No chunking uses the first chunk. This is the same as having no chunks at all and using truncated input.

$$w_{a_c} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } c = 0 \\ 0, & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

5.5.2 Mean Chunk Fusion

Mean Chunk Fusion takes the mean of all aspect embeddings related to an aspect.

$$w_{a_c} = \frac{1}{|C|} \quad (16)$$

5.5.3 CLS-Gating Chunk Fusion

CLS-Gating Chunk Fusion is inspired by CLS-Gating in aspect fusion. The ECLS of every chunk is used to calculate logits for each aspect and the CLS token through a linear layer, i.e., $Linear(E_{CLS_c}) \in \mathbb{R}^{|A|+1}$. These logits are softmaxed to get the chunk weights per aspect.

$$w_{a_c} = \frac{e^{Linear(E_{CLS_c})_a}}{\sum_{c \in C} e^{Linear(E_{CLS_c})_a}} \quad (17)$$

⁸ 94% of the queries have less than or exactly 512 tokens (see 4.3.4).

5.5.4 Attention Chunk Fusion

Attention Chunk Fusion, however, transmits the idea of the AEN and assigns weights to each chunk for each aspect by using attention. By using attention, all chunk embeddings of one aspect interact with each other. Attention scores for each chunk per aspect are the result.

Analogous to the AEN, a trainable query parameter is defined. But here it has a shape different shape⁹: $Q, P_C^Q \in \mathbb{R}^{|A|+1 \times 1 \times H}$. The other parameters have the same shape as in the AEN. Therefore are $K, V \in \mathbb{R}^{|A|+1 \times |C| \times H}$. The result vector has the same size as Q. By squeezing the second dimension, the extra chunk dimension is eliminated.

As the previously presented methods, attention-based chunk fusion also computes chunk weights for each aspect, which are represented in the attention scores. But different from the other methods, it uses matrix multiplications and can be described via the attention formula:

$$E_a = \text{Attention}(P_C^Q W^Q, E_{AC} W^K, E_{AC} W^V) \quad (18)$$

In this paper, chunking is only used together with aspect learning and the model using chunking is called **Chunked Multi-Aspect Dense Retrieval with Aspect Learning Model (CMADRAL Model)**.

Note that if documents are too large, enough memory or a chunk limit is needed because, as with the Longformer, memory usage grows linearly with documents size.

5.6 Recap

This chapter explained the components of the CMADRALN model. It went over BERT as a base encoder, aspect extraction and aspect prediction, as well as aspect fusion. These components are used for MADRAL. It additionally offered improvements for them and added a chunking layer to handle large documents. The proposed model uses the explicit CLS token embedding instead of the implicit “OTHER” aspect, the extra loss for continuous aspects, CLS-Gating aspect fusion, and CLS-Gating-based chunking on the document site. A visual overview of the model is provided in Figure 21 in Appendix C.

⁹ The +1 in the first dimension is for the E_{CLS} , which is concatenated with the aspect embeddings. The 1 in the second dimension is used as the merging dimension for chunks and squeezed away after attention calculation.

6 Experimental Setup

This chapter explains the experimental setup. It shows how to pre-train and fine-tune the model presented in the previous chapter and provides an overview of evaluation criteria for the results presented in the next chapter.

6.1 Requirements

To efficiently train the models, the datasets must be prepared. Queries, documents, and relevance scores are loaded into RAM. The query and document labels are converted into binary class label tensors. The classes for each aspect are the categories in the aspect vocabulary V_a . If the model with special treatment for continuous is used, the labels are the min and max values of the aspect annotations for continuous aspects. When a continuous aspect has only one annotation, the min and max values are the same. The continuous labels are normalized on a per-aspect basis using min-max normalization to scale the values to the interval $[0, 1]$. This enables efficient training because neural networks cannot handle large numbers well.

Additionally, the dataset is shuffled and the train, validate, and test splits are made if no splits were saved. The subsets use 70%, 10%, and 20% of the whole dataset, respectively. After splitting, the indices are saved to a file to ensure consistent datasets over multiple training processes. The only exception to this is the fine-tuning dataset, since its indices are calculated based on the other datasets.

The model weights are saved after every epoch to load them if the process crashes or previous models perform better on the validation data.

6.2 Input Preprocessing

An input text has to be tokenized in order for it to be fed into the BERT model. BertTokenizerFast is used for this task, as it utilizes an efficient Rust implementation and is around five times faster than the default BertTokenizer on the document dataset.

After tokenizing the input text, the tokens are chunked into blocks of 512 tokens—the maximum sequence length for BERT. Since a chunk is a single input for the BERT model, each one gets a CLS token at the beginning and a SEP token either at the first index with no attention—where the attention mask is zero—or at the last position of the chunk. To avoid cutting edges in which more context might be helpful at the beginning of a chunk, a 10-token overlap between the chunks is used.

It might be worth stating, that in the implementation, chunks are used as a list of inputs and not introduced as an extra tensor dimension. This has the advantage that they are not separated when using multiple GPUs. They belong together and must be passed through the same model after one another.

Since BERT is a Masked Language Model (MLM) and learns embeddings via masked input, masking is applied to each chunk. Following best practices, 15% of all tokens are masked, of which 80% are replaced with the actual [MASK] token, 10% with a random token from the tokenizer vocabulary, and 10% are left as they are (Devlin et al., 2018). The 15% selected tokens are used for MLM-Loss calculation.

In the last step of preprocessing, the batch labels are sent to the GPU to enable faster training. All other tensors created during the process are already initialized with the correct device. Putting it all together, the output of preprocessing is a list of encoded chunks, a list of masked token labels, and batch labels with all tensors present on the GPU.

6.3 Pre-Training

In the pre-training phase, the model is trained using the query and document datasets. Since the query dataset is larger, it is taken as the primary dataset, which determines the steps per epoch. The document dataset is therefore used as the secondary dataset, from which the next batch is taken continuously. This way, the documents already had multiple epochs after one query epoch.

The pre-training aims to develop the encoders text understanding, and if used, learn the aspect embeddings with aspect learning. This is achieved by combining the MLM-Loss (Devlin et al., 2018) and the Aspect Prediction Loss (equation (9) and possibly (10)) as follows:

$$L = L_{MLM} + \sum_{a \in A \setminus \{OTHER\}} L_{AP}^a \quad (19)$$

The MLM-Loss is the cross-entropy loss of the token prediction for all masked tokens. Note that there is no aspect prediction loss for the “OTHER” aspect, as it does not have any annotations. If aspect learning is not used, the MLM-Loss is the only loss function.

The total pre-training loss for the model is the combined loss of the two encoders.

$$L_{pre} = L_{pre}^q + L_{pre}^d \quad (20)$$

6.4 Fine-Tuning

During fine-tuning, the learned text understanding and aspects should be utilized to optimize the model’s similarity predictions between queries and documents and improve its ability to rank documents for a query. To achieve this, pointwise similarity loss is used instead of pairwise loss.

To compute the in-batch similarity scores between queries and documents, their embeddings are normalized and matrix-multiplied, which provides the cosine similarity for each possible query-document pair in the batch.

$$rel(q, d) = \left\| \text{Encoder}_q(q) \right\|_2 \circ \left\| \text{Encoder}_d(d) \right\|_2 \quad (21)$$

$$REL = \left\| \text{Encoder}_q(Q_B) \right\|_2 \left\| \text{Encoder}_d(D_B) \right\|_2^T \quad (22)$$

Where *Encoder* represents the corresponding query or document encoder-arm of the model. Note that the relevance scores from cosine similarity are between -1 and 1 instead of 0 to 1.

This way, not only query-document pairs from the dataset are used but also random in-batch pairs for diversification. Thus, if 16 relevant query-document pairs are used as batch size, then $16 \cdot 16 = 256$ relevance scores are used for the in-batch loss calculation. Since the labels are continuous, the mean squared error loss is leveraged to predict the exact relevance scores (Lin et al., 2020, P. 114). This way, the model also learns relative differences between the pairs, not just “relevant” or “irrelevant” as with binary relevance labels. This might also help the model rank documents better.

To correctly apply the MSE, the relevance scores from equation (21) are scaled from the interval $[-1, 1]$ to the interval $[0, 1]$:

$$rel_{scaled}(q, d) = \frac{rel(q, d) + 1}{2} \quad (23)$$

As evaluated in 7.2.3, it is also helpful to add a bit of pre-training loss to the MSE loss. Putting it all together, the fine-tuning loss is calculated as follows:

$$L_{fine} = L_{MSE} + \lambda \cdot L_{pre}, \quad \lambda \in \mathbb{R} \quad (24)$$

Where λ is a hyperparameter chosen such that the pre-training loss only contributes around one tenth of the MSE loss to consider it, but not make it the main task.

6.5 Training Parameters

The training process depends not only on the model, datasets, and loss functions, but also on a list of hyperparameters and other choices. For most of them, the transformer paper (Vaswani et al., 2017) or original MADR paper (Kong et al., 2022) were consulted. All models use the same training parameters to keep the training fair and comparable.

As an optimizer, AdamW was used with a learning rate of $1e-4$. It already uses a weight decay regularization of $1e-2$. To add more regularization, there is a dropout in or after each layer with a dropout rate of 0.1.

For the batch size, 128 was found to provide the best results (Appendix D). Although not possible due to hardware limitations, gradient accumulation is applied to minibatches to still update only on every 128th item. Because the dataset contains much more queries than documents, the document encoder tends to overfit very fast (Appendix D). Because of that, a different batch size for queries and documents is chosen. While queries use a mini-batch size of 64, which accumulates to 128, documents use a mini-batch size of 5 to use all five GPUs efficiently, which accumulates to 10 documents per batch. This applies to all non-chunked models.

Chunked models are even more limited with respect to GPU memory. While still only using 5 documents, the maximum number of queries that fit on the GPUs in addition to the document chunks is 15. The nearest multiple of it to 128 is 120, which is selected as the batch size for chunked models. While it is a rather uncommon number, this is the most efficient way to use the provided hardware. Since fine-tuning uses query-document pairs, the mini-batch size for chunked and non-chunked models is 5 and 64 here, which results in 25 and 4,096 comparisons, respectively.

Models are trained until the validation loss—validation MSE loss only for fine-tuning—increases or the learning rate falls below $1e-7$. A ReduceOnPlateau learning rate scheduler is used to decrease the learning rate when the model’s loss has not improved by at least 1% compared to the previous epoch. Previous works have shown that a step decay in the learning rate is very efficient (Ge et al., 2019; Lewkowycz, 2021; You et al., 2019). It helps the model learn coarse patterns with higher learning rates and optimize on details with lower ones. This way, no training budget has to be defined. The models are saved and validated after each epoch, and the variant with the lowest validation loss is chosen for fine-tuning. During fine-tuning, the chunked model is saved and validated every 64 steps.

To preserve start weights and explore the loss space slowly before building more and more momentum, a warm-up is used. This prevents optimizing in the wrong direction too fast and destroying weights. A warm-up of 0.1 epochs is used since it has shown good results, while 1 warm-up epoch guided the document encoder to a bad local minimum (Appendix D).

6.6 Model Implementation

The original paper (Kong et al., 2022) already compared the models BiBERT, MtBERT, MADR, and MADRAL. BiBERT (Reimers & Gurevych, 2019) is a baseline model with two BERT encoder arms using the same BERT model as MADR, but without replacing the last transformer block. The CLS token is used as an embedding. The model is only trained with MLM loss as a pre-training loss. MtBERT (Kong et al., 2022) is a **multi-task** baseline model. It follows the same principle as BiBERT, but learns the CLS token with aspect learning during pre-training. Hence, it uses the same losses as MADRAL. MADR and MADRAL are models presented in the previous chapter using the “OTHER” and no chunking. The first one is without aspect learning, and the second one is with. MADR is trained with the same losses as BiBERT.

The paper has shown that MADRAL is the best-performing model, followed by MADR and MtBERT, which perform almost equally, and BiBERT performs worst. The fact that MtBERT and MADR perform approximately equal, but MADR is not trained with aspect annotations, shows that the model architecture of MADR fits the retrieval task well. The superior performance of MADRAL further shows the importance of aspect learning for the model’s performance (Kong et al., 2022).

However, other experiments have shown that the original MADRAL performs even worse than BiBERT (Bi et al., 2024). Their suggestion is to use the explicit CLS token

instead of the implicit “OTHER” aspect to drastically improve the model’s performance because the “OTHER” aspect is insufficiently learned during fine-tuning.

Since the comparison between BiBERT, MtBERT, MADR, and MADRAL has already been made, this paper focuses on the improvements. It investigates the influence of using the CLS token as an explicit aspect and further evaluates self-made improvements like numerical treatment and chunking. Therefore, the following models are evaluated and compared during this work:

- MADRAL: the model presented in the previous chapter with aspect learning.
- MADRAL-CLS: the same model as MADRAL, but uses the CLS token instead of the “OTHER” aspect.
- MADRALN: this model adds the special treatment of continuous aspects to MADRAL-CLS.
- CMADRALN: same as MADRALN, but adds CLS-Gating Chunk Fusion. To prevent OutOfMemory errors, the chunk count is limited to 30 chunks, which covers 98% of the documents.

A visualization of the model architectures is provided in Appendix C.

Other works (Bi et al., 2024; Sun et al., 2024) have also reported that the best value for λ in equation (24) is 0, while Kong et al. stated that a bit of aspect prediction loss would be helpful. This is also a target of the proposed model evaluation.

6.7 Retrieval

ScaNN is used for the final retrieval test. The checkpoint of the model to be tested is loaded and used to compute document embeddings offline. These embeddings are given to ScaNN, which is initialized with the following parameters:

Table 3: ScaNN parameters.

Parameter	Value
num_neighbors	200 (max(cutoffs))
dimensions_per_block	2
num_leaves	50
num_leaves_to_search	10
training_sample_size	250_000
reorder	200 (same as num_neighbors)

The ScaNN setup follows the official rule-of-thumb guideline for large datasets (*ScaNN Algorithms and Configuration*, 2020) to simulate production use with a large dataset.

The query test dataset is then used to evaluate the retrieval by encoding queries with the loaded model and passing the resulting query embeddings into the ScaNN searcher to

retrieve document indices. The metrics are calculated using the relevance scores from the fine-tune dataset.

6.8 Docker

A Docker image is provided to test retrieval time and make manual tests in a production simulation. It uses `python:3.12` as a base image and has the necessary requirements installed. The container loads the weights of a mounted checkpoint at startup and, if not already done, encodes all documents in a mounted directory and saves the result for faster restarts. It provides a lightweight API using `uvicorn` and `FastAPI` with only one query endpoint. This endpoint takes a `q` (query), an optional `cutoff` or `limit`, and an optional `expand` flag as parameters. The retrieval follows the same procedure described in 6.7. Depending on the `expand` flag, either the document IDs or the whole documents are returned. This option is used for testing purposes only and should be paired with a low cutoff because the length of the documents causes a large body and therefore increases the response time.

6.9 Evaluation

To evaluate the model's performance, this section is about which metrics are measured in which way and gives some reference values and recommendations for the final evaluation in chapter 7.

6.9.1 Metrics

For different phases of the model, different metrics are evaluated. For pre-training, both precision and recall are evaluated. As many correct aspect category predictions as possible are wanted (recall) while not annotating too many false categories (precision). So the F1-score is taken as the primary measure for that phase.

During the fine-tuning phase, precision and recall are not too relevant because it is a regression task. They are useful to see how well the model predicts relevance scores into categories (6.9.2), but during fine-tuning the ability to rank is more important. Therefore, the NDCG is the most important metric, as it measures ranking and makes result lists comparable. This also applies to the final retrieval or production stage, where also the retrieval time is evaluated. To measure the ability of the model to predict query-document similarity and not only its ability to rank, retrieval is also measured in terms of precision and recall. To balance both metrics and see the impact of the result list length, they are measured at different cutoffs. The more documents are retrieved, the higher the possibility of relevant documents, which supports the recall. But the other side of the coin is that more irrelevant documents might be retrieved, which hurts precision. So, both metrics work against each other.

6.9.2 Measurement

For retrieval tasks, those binary metrics are measured using the relevance score dataset. The documents are divided into different relevance categories. The following figure shows the mean recall per query at different cutoffs, i.e., result list lengths, and thresholds at which a document is considered relevant. Thresholds are: 0.1, 0.2, 0.25, 0.3, 0.33, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.67, 0.7, 0.75, 0.8, 0.9, and 0.95.

Figure 9: Mean recall per query by cutoffs and thresholds.

Based on their similarity scores, the documents are divided into four categories: irrelevant (< 0.4), slightly relevant (≥ 0.4), relevant (≥ 0.5), and highly relevant (≥ 0.67). 0.4 is chosen because there is still a noticeable overlap between queries and documents, while increasing the number of relevant documents by 5% when taking 50% as a baseline. With a 50% threshold, 10% of all documents are considered relevant, while with a 40% threshold, that number grows to 15% of slightly relevant results. From 0.67, the recall per query is quite similar. Reports are done on relevant documents (≥ 0.5) if no relevance measure is given. Otherwise, metrics are signed with the threshold percentage behind the name, for example, Recall67@10 for the recall of highly relevant documents at cutoff 10.

This categorization simplifies the monitoring of metrics regarding relevant documents and helps with the decision for the most significant cutoff. Precision, recall, and NDCG are reported at cutoffs of 5, 10, 50, and 200. As shown in Figure 9, higher cutoffs do not provide significant improvement in recall. Papers have also evaluated that user attention drastically decreases with a rising rank in the result list and that there is an additional drop when the user has to go onto the next result page (Granka et al., 2004). This can be

prevented with endless scroll, but still, the first 10 results are the most influential ones in terms of user attention. Therefore, 10 is considered the most important cutoff to measure for the search engine and it is also approximately equivalent to the length of an imaginable search result list view. 200 is chosen as the maximum list length, thus the k for ANN search, because the highly relevant documents reach a recall of around 95% at this point.

During the final retrieval, the retrieved documents all get a score of one for the binary metrics because they are retrieved and therefore considered relevant to the user; during fine-tuning, the predicted document score is used.

The best models during pre-training are chosen based on validation loss after each epoch. In the fine-tuning phase, the best models are selected using the fine-tune validation loss and validation NDCG values after every 1,000 steps.

Using the best models, documents are encoded offline first and then retrieved using ScaNN. Retrieval is done with a) test queries only and b) all queries to see how well the model generalizes, while the whole document dataset is used to mirror real-world retrieval scenarios. Retrieval times are measured for following cases using the Docker container and the query test dataset:

1. IDs only at maximum cutoff of 200.
2. Full documents at a cutoff of 10 and 20 for one result page.

All results are reported on the test sets. Paired t-tests are used to mark statistically significant differences with a p-value < 0.05 .

6.9.3 Reference Values and Recommendations

To finally decide whether a model is good or not, metrics at the cutoff @10 are used. To provide a recommendation on whether the model is good or not, precision is divided into five steps. These guidelines automatically influence the reference values for recall. Since the NDCG is a metric, which compares the ranking of the result list with the best possible ranking, NDCG scores can be seen as percentages of the best ranking result. A summary of the chosen recommendations is presented in the following table:

Table 4: Recommendations of model performance evaluation.

	P@10	R@10	NDCG@10
Very Good	80%	65%	0.85
Good	60%	49%	0.7
Okay	40%	33%	0.5
Questionable	20%	16%	0.3

Recommendations for recall refer to highly relevant documents and are calculated by multiplying the P@10 value with the mean recall per query at cutoff 10, which is the maximum possible mean recall. Everything below “Questionable” is considered useless.

6.10 Recap

This chapter went over the whole training process and experimental setup. Datasets are loaded and split into subsets before training. The input texts are preprocessed using techniques like chunking and masking. Also, the labels are prepared by transforming the aspect annotations into classification labels or possibly regression labels. The pre-training aims to teach the model text and aspect understanding, while fine-tuning is primarily used for ranking. The researched models are trained using the same setup with the AdamW optimizer, a warm-up, a ReduceLROnPlateau learning rate scheduler, and a learning rate of $1e-4$. For the different phases of the model, different metrics are used. Precision and recall for pre-training and NDCG for fine-tuning and retrieval. Precision and recall, as well as NDCG, are also evaluated for the retrieval task using different cutoffs, above all @10. To measure retrieval times, a Docker container is provided to simulate a production environment.

7 Results

This chapter presents the results of this work. It contains comparisons of the final models and provides insights into training metrics and side experiments. Furthermore, small case studies to support the understanding of the models are included.

7.1 Overall Results

The overall results are shown in Table 5. The overall low is precision probably caused of an unbalanced dataset because there are way more negative aspect annotations than positive ones. The models’ performances struggle and this might be because of the little document dataset. Other decisions like using CLS-Gating instead of aspect fusion and too little training times also play a role. Unfortunately, all models perform poorly, indicating that more work has to done here.

Table 5: Results for MADRM.s.

	P@5	P@10	R@5	R@10	NDCG@5	NDCG@10
MADRAL	0.097	0.100	0.008	0.014	0.274	0.241
MADRAL-CLS	0.101	0.103	0.007	0.013	0.274	0.237
MADRALN	0.113	0.112	0.008	0.013	0.297	0.299
CMADRALN	0.107	0.107	0.008	0.012	0.305	0.309
	P@50	P@200	R@50	R@200	NDCG@50	NDCG@200
MADRAL	0.109	0.104	0.038	0.147	0.345	0.297
MADRAL-CLS	0.112	0.107	0.037	0.141	0.342	0.292
MADRALN	0.105	0.102	0.043	0.137	0.299	0.296
CMADRALN	0.104	0.097	0.049	0.139	0.306	0.298

7.2 Training, Findings and Experiments

After discussing the overall results, this section dives deeper into the training process and model architecture. Training results, findings, and experiments are presented from pre-training over fine-tuning to whole model interpretability.

7.2.1 Chunk Fusion Networks

To select one of the chunk fusion possibilities presented in section 5.5, the CMADRAL document encoder was tested in isolation, which means that it was tested without the query encoder. The following figure shows the results:

Figure 10: Comparison of the isolated loss for different chunk fusion techniques.

Using only the first chunk works surprisingly well. Note that this is only possible in isolation. When paired with the query encoder, the model has to sync the aspect embeddings, which can be harder and is not explicitly researched here. Also, very interestingly, the mean chunk fusion did not work well at all. It is even worse than only taking the first one. This is probably because the embeddings of the separate chunks neutralize each other when being summed. A better approach might be to take max pooling instead of mean pooling, but this is not further researched here.

Attention- and CLS-Gating-based fusion techniques both work quite well. Unfortunately, the training process for attention-based chunk fusion was interrupted because it did not stop naturally as mean and first chunk fusion. Nevertheless, it is visible that it takes more time to converge, although it might work as well as CLS-Gating. Additionally, it needs more parameters and has a higher time complexity. That is why CLS-Gating-based chunk fusion is used to train the models in this paper.

7.2.2 Comparison of Document Preprocessing

During Aspect Learning, different types of preprocessed documents were fit into the isolated CMADRAL document encoder to compare aspect learning performances. On the one hand, the default compressed documents, as described in 4.5, were used. On the other hand, it was tried to further shrink the token size of documents by breaking up the JSON structure and removing the curly brackets and quotation marks in documents. It was assumed that this would not affect the model's performance but would speed up the training process as fewer chunks had to be processed. Figure 11 shows the results:

Figure 11: Aspect Learning losses of models trained with JSON vs. text.

Surprisingly, it seems like the JSON structure helps the model understand the document structure and extract aspects from it. While the model trained with the simplified documents stuck after 18 epochs with a training loss of 40.34, the model trained with JSON improved for 61 epochs, down to a training loss of 20.29. Table 6 provides additional metrics for both models at epoch 18 using the validation set and the last epoch using the test dataset and evaluation mode, respectively. The test loss is also added as an additional epoch in Figure 11.

Table 6: Comparison of models trained with JSON and simplified documents.

Metric	JSON Val E 18	Text Val E 18	JSON Test	Text Test
Loss	37.06	40.74	5.94	26.17
Precision	0.75	0.74	0.90	0.74
Recall	0.32	0.32	0.59	0.36
F1	0.45	0.44	0.71	0.48

7.2.3 Shared and Unshared APN

During fine-tuning MADRAL, different model architectures were tested. By mistake, a shared APN was used at first. This surprisingly worked, but was unstable during fine-tuning. The following figures show a comparison of two setups during fine-tuning:

1. Unshared APN, only fine-tuning loss (MSE, Unshared APN)
2. Shared APN, pre-training and fine-tuning loss (MSE and AP, Shared APN)

Figure 12: Comparison of NDCG values for different fine-tuning setups.

Figure 13: Comparison of fine-tuning losses for different setups.

Figure 14: Comparison of query and document aspect prediction losses for different fine-tuning setups.

Figure 12 shows the NDCG values, which is the main metric while fine-tuning. You can see that the shared APN is always performing better than the unshared one. Furthermore, there is a sudden drop in the unshared variation after two epochs. This is also re-

flected in the fine-tuning loss in Figure 13. Looking at Figure 14, which displays the aspect prediction losses for queries and documents, respectively, it becomes conceivable that these losses also contribute to model performance. As the loss for the documents of the first setup rises dramatically, the fine-tuning loss rises as well, while the NDCG drops. Interestingly, the query loss drops too but is not stable either.

The assumption that the aspect prediction losses contribute to the model’s ranking performance and have an influence on the fine-tuning loss seems to make sense in terms of the model architecture. The aspect embeddings are explicitly trained on a given vocabulary during pre-training and represent the separate aspect information. The fine-tuning process should then use this information and learn a smart gating fusion to represent the whole query or document with only a single embedding. Asymmetric aspect embeddings, which are learned independently, make it hard to compare the different embeddings. That might be the reason why the query and document losses in Figure 14 diverge. The model probably tries to sync the embeddings. A shared APN also improves the model’s interpretability.

7.2.4 Different Values for λ

As shown in Appendix E, it seems that using a bit of pre-train loss during fine-tuning is indeed improving the model’s performance. Table 7 shows the comparison of their retrieval metrics. The variant using pre-training loss beats the other variant in all metrics and is hence chosen for all fine-tuning. It ensures the model’s interpretability.

Table 7: Comparison of retrieval performance for different λ values.

	$\lambda=0$	$\lambda=0.01$
Precision@10	0.098	0.107
NDCG@10	0.272	0.309*
Recall@10	0.005	0.012*

* signalizes statistical relevant changes over $\lambda=0$.

7.2.5 Embeddings Tables

To understand the semantic similarities learned by the model, the aspect embeddings tables of the CMADRALN model are examined. The top four similar values to a selected value of the aspects `carline`, `color_out`, `manufacturer`, and `equipment` are listed in Table 8 and Table 9. Similarity scores are calculated using the cosine similarity of the value embeddings. When values are stated twice, it means that they are two different entities with different IDs in the vocabulary but share the same descriptive text.

For `carline`, it is visible that the values are all very similar, which means that the model understands this aspect quite well. The fact that yellow, orange, and violet are similar to red is also reasonable in terms of their proximity on the color wheel. Looking at the `equipment` example, you can see that the model finds two very similar equipment items

with different PR numbers¹⁰, but also ranks two completely different values highly as well. This demonstrates that the model learned a bit about the aspect value similarities, but there is still room for improvement.

Table 8: Examples of semantically related aspect values for `carline`, `color_out`, and `manufacturer`.

<code>carline</code>	<code>color_out</code>	<code>manufacturer</code>
(1.000) Audi A3 Sportback	(1.000) red	(1.000) Audi
(0.665) Audi S3 Sportback	(0.567) yellow	(0.518) BMW
(0.650) Audi A3 Limousine	(0.563) orange	(0.479) Mercedes
(0.649) Audi A3 Sportback	(0.552) violet	(0.476) SEAT
(0.646) Audi A5 Sportback	(0.543) other	(0.473) VW

Table 9: Example of semantically related aspect values for `equipment`.

<code>equipment</code>
(1.000) Matrix LED headlights with dynamic indicators front and rear
(0.621) Matrix LED headlights with dynamic light staging and dynamic indicator lights
(0.611) Head-up Display
(0.610) Trunk floor mat
(0.607) Matrix LED headlights with dynamic light staging and dynamic indicator lights

7.2.6 Interpretability

MADRAL provides improved interpretability through the aspect embeddings, embedding tables, and aspect fusion. These components enable detailed analysis at different stages of the model and hence contribute to the understanding of how embeddings are created. This subsection provides an insight into the separate components of the CMADRALN query encoder.

Figure 15 shows the attention scores for chosen aspects over the tokens of an example query in German, English, and Spanish. The fields with more attention are more colored. Although the model was only trained on German data, it is nevertheless able to attend to the correct tokens. You can clearly see which tokens are used for which aspect, and the learned choices totally make sense.

The aspect embeddings from the AEN are then passed through the APN to obtain the aspect predictions, which are shown in Figure 16. The same German query as in Figure 15 is used. As you can see, the `carline` and `manufacturer` aspects are performing subop-

¹⁰ PR numbers are used to identify car equipment.

tinally. The correct predictions are in the top five, but their predicted probabilities are too low. The color aspect, however, corresponds to the query. Taking a look at the continuous values for which an interval is predicted, it is visible that the year is predicted nearly perfectly. The interval for the mileage aspect seems to go in the right direction, since the min value is very low and the max value is higher, but the max is not high enough to represent the interval reliably. The aspect prediction performance in other languages is a bit worse for categorical aspects, but very similar for continuous ones.

At the last stage of the encoder, there is the AFN to fuse the aspect embeddings into one representation for the query. Unfortunately, it has a very poor performance. The aspects from the query are not used, while completely unrelated aspects, like previous owners and prices, are scored much higher. The weights for the chosen aspects for the example query are shown in Table 10.

To sum up, the encoder becomes worse with every layer. This is not a problem of the model architecture but of insufficient training and training data. You can see that the AEN is performing well, but the aspect embedding tables are not yet trained enough. Furthermore, the poor performance of the AFN is a bit surprising but reasonable because the errors add up. Poor aspect embeddings lead to poor representations, which makes good merging impossible. At this point, it might be worth using Presence Weighting (5.4.2) instead of CLS-Gating for the AFN, as this already learns presence weights during pre-training and makes it impossible for the model to use unrelated aspects for the final representation. The hoped-for superiority of CLS-Gating might come with additional training but could not be reproduced during this work.

Token	[CLS]	ich	mochte	alle	silber	##nen	audi	a3	sport	##backs	aus	dem	jahr
color_out	0,000	0,008	0,031	0,029	0,846	0,079	0,000	0,001	0,000	0,001	0,000	0,000	0,000
manufacturer	0,000	0,156	0,011	0,009	0,009	0,002	0,313	0,234	0,089	0,109	0,000	0,000	0,000
carline	0,000	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,002	0,001	0,403	0,522	0,020	0,049	0,000	0,000	0,000
mileage_total	0,000	0,000	0,003	0,003	0,002	0,003	0,002	0,003	0,005	0,006	0,007	0,011	0,012
model_year	0,000	0,005	0,039	0,034	0,012	0,032	0,002	0,004	0,009	0,010	0,100	0,189	0,291

Token	2020	,	die	weniger	als	943	##91	km	gefahr	##en	sind	.	[SEP]
color_out	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,001	0,001	0,000	0,001	0,001
manufacturer	0,000	0,000	0,001	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,014	0,010	0,003	0,004	0,034
carline	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
mileage_total	0,017	0,025	0,157	0,094	0,103	0,157	0,209	0,134	0,002	0,012	0,010	0,012	0,011
model_year	0,173	0,060	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,015	0,013	0,010

Token	[CLS]	i	would	like	all	silver	audi	a3	sport	##backs	from	2020
color_out	0,000	0,087	0,135	0,311	0,034	0,313	0,005	0,015	0,010	0,017	0,001	0,000
manufacturer	0,000	0,517	0,036	0,047	0,012	0,026	0,144	0,089	0,028	0,032	0,000	0,000
carline	0,000	0,003	0,001	0,002	0,000	0,001	0,577	0,401	0,011	0,003	0,000	0,000
mileage_total	0,000	0,003	0,001	0,002	0,005	0,018	0,006	0,008	0,011	0,011	0,008	0,006
model_year	0,000	0,008	0,003	0,013	0,011	0,011	0,005	0,007	0,015	0,017	0,366	0,363

Token	that	have	driven	less	than	943	##91	km	.	[SEP]
color_out	0,008	0,006	0,002	0,003	0,002	0,003	0,001	0,001	0,025	0,020
manufacturer	0,010	0,016	0,006	0,001	0,000	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,003	0,033
carline	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000
mileage_total	0,008	0,003	0,002	0,146	0,118	0,178	0,248	0,172	0,017	0,029
model_year	0,093	0,061	0,008	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,006	0,014

Token	[CLS]	qui	##sier	##a	todos	los	audi	a3	sport	##back	plate	##ados	a	partir
color_out	0,000	0,035	0,043	0,010	0,017	0,015	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,000	0,823	0,039	0,003	0,000
manufacturer	0,000	0,039	0,039	0,016	0,034	0,032	0,134	0,128	0,086	0,082	0,020	0,021	0,275	0,000
carline	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,394	0,469	0,061	0,070	0,002	0,001	0,001	0,000
mileage_total	0,000	0,002	0,003	0,020	0,005	0,005	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,002	0,007	0,000	0,000
model_year	0,000	0,039	0,017	0,065	0,073	0,111	0,015	0,017	0,027	0,033	0,031	0,145	0,037	0,037

Token	de	2020	que	haya	##n	reconstru	menos	de	943	##91	km	.	[SEP]
color_out	0,000	0,000	0,001	0,003	0,000	0,002	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,004	0,001
manufacturer	0,000	0,000	0,001	0,019	0,001	0,030	0,001	0,000	0,001	0,000	0,000	0,007	0,035
carline	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0
mileage_total	0,000	0,001	0,004	0,005	0,062	0,010	0,121	0,069	0,249	0,264	0,157	0,005	0,004
model_year	0,066	0,182	0,042	0,004	0,013	0,002	0,001	0,002	0,001	0,001	0,001	0,014	0,024

Figure 15: Attention scores for chosen aspects over an example query in German, English, and Spanish from CMADRALN’s AEN.

	Audi TT Roadster	Audi A1 allstreet	Audi A1 allstreet	Audi A3 Sportback	Audi RS 3 Sportback
carline	0,238	0,197	0,173	0,167	0,153

	Silber (silver)	Grün (green)	Beige (beige)	Blau (blue)	Rot (red)
color_out	0,636	0,148	0,082	0,064	0,031

	SEAT	Audi	BMW	VW Nutzfahrzeuge	SKODA
manufacturer	0,160	0,024	0,006	0,006	0,005

	min	max
model_year	0,762	0,755
value	2023	2023

	min	max
mileage_total	0,028	0,168
value	2500 km	5038 km

Figure 16: Aspect predictions from CMADRALN’s APN.

Table 10: Aspect fusion weights from CMADRALN’s AFN.

	carline	color_out	manufacturer	model_year	mileage_total
Fusion weight	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.001

7.3 Requirements

This section covers the fulfillment status of requirements (RQs). Each subsection refers to the associated point from section 1.2.

7.3.1 RQ 1: Large JSON files as documents

This requirement is fulfilled with the introduction of the CFN, as described in 5.5. This way, long documents are supported. The fact that the model can understand JSON structure is shown in 7.2.2. Furthermore, when tested with shared APNs, both encoders reach presentable pre-training metrics. Queries reach a precision of 86% and a recall of 84%, while documents get 89% and 59%, respectively. It follows from this that the model can handle the JSON format.

7.3.2 RQ 2: Large Document Corpus

This requirement is respected during retrieval by using ScaNN for ANN search, but it cannot be tested at scale due to a lack of resources. Having more documents is no problem in terms of retrieval time, but it has an impact on offline encoding of documents. This process takes more time and requires more space. 1926 documents are equivalent to around 13 MB of embeddings. That means that 100,000 to 500,000 documents would require 675 to 3,375 MB. This still fits into RAM and makes a large document corpus only more time-consuming during training and offline encoding. That is also why a GPU for document encoding should be used. When encoding the small document dataset used in this work with CPU, it takes around 45 minutes. With just a single GPU, it is a matter of seconds.

The encoding process is analogous to the indexing process used for full-text search. The advantage here is that the created index is dense and, thus, not only supports semantic similarity but can carry more complex information.

7.3.3 RQ 3: Multilingualism

As shown in 7.2.6, the model preserves its knowledge about multilingual texts from the chosen BERT checkpoint (5.1). This is a good starting point, but multilingual training samples should be used in the future to train reliable aspect embeddings.

7.3.4 RQ 4: Docker Container with API

A Docker image with a simple API is for testing purposes is provided (6.8).

7.3.5 RQ 5: Response Time

Response times for different query configurations were measured using the Docker container. 1,000 queries were used per configuration. The mean retrieval time for documents IDs using the full cutoff with a random query was 0.12s. When retrieving whole documents with a cutoff 10, the mean retrieval time was 1.01s. You have to add network traffic when using it as an external API, but these times lie perfectly within the set boundaries. Since the normal use case will be to retrieve IDs only, the API can be considered to respond “immediately”.

7.4 Research Objectives

This section covers the fulfillment status of research objectives (ROs). Each subsection refers to the associated point from section 1.3.

7.4.1 RO 1: Applicability of MADR for Large JSON Files

Following the recommendations in Table 4, and the results in Table 5, the model is not yet ready not use. The weak results are based on an insufficient dataset and not enough training time. But the models show promising intentions, making it an interesting target for further research. That the model is able to handle large JSON files is shown in 7.2.2.

7.4.2 RO 2: Using a Few Hundred Aspects

The models trained during this work use more than 200 aspects, which does not seem to be problematic. Difficulties that arise because of weaknesses in the project setup, but not because of the models not being capable of the number of aspects.

7.4.3 RO 3: Special Number Treatment

As shown in Table 5, the adjustment of the APN with a special loss for continuous values outperforms the otherwise same model, MADRAL-CLS. So, predicting intervals for continuous values works better than predicting all possible number annotations in the vocabulary and is also not limited to those values as the interval itself is made of two continuous values.

7.4.4 RO 4: Chunking

Although the overall results do not show a performance gain of CMADRALN, the chunking model shows its strength during the pre-training, as can be seen in Table 11.

Table 11: Comparison of MADRALN and CMADRALN pre-training metrics.

Metric	MADRALN	CMADRALN
Loss	28.98	20.82
Query Loss	11.10	9.61
Document Loss	17.87	11.21
Query Precision	0.005	0.007
Document Precision	0.110	0.118
Query Recall	0.736	0.754
Document Recall	0.752	0.811

CMADRALN beats MADRALN in all metrics. What is particularly noticeable is that the document loss is more than halved when chunking is applied. It is interesting that the queries also get an improvement, although nothing has changed on the query encoder side. This is probably related to the better understanding of documents, which helps the model find better shared aspect embeddings. To sum up, chunking helps the model understand large documents better by a large margin during pre-training, but currently, this does not get reflected in the fine-tuning. This could mean, that CMDARALN needs longer fine-tuning than the other models.

7.4.5 RO 5: Explore Similarity Search with different Dimensionalities

This work does not use any further projection of the 768-dimensional embeddings. There are no efficiency problems, and as shown in 7.3.2, the size of embedding is manageable for the given document corpus. So currently, no projection to fewer dimensions like 128 is necessary.

7.5 Recap

This chapter went over the results and a few experiments. MADRALN shows best performance, although CMADRALN was strong after pre-training. This implies limitations of the time that was taken to fine-tune the model, indicating even more time is needed.

This chapter also provides insights into how the model works and its interpretability. Requirements and research objectives, were evaluated, showing that the developed models are not yet ready for use but offer a good foundation for further research.

8 Limitations and Future Work

Multi-Aspect Dense Retrieval is a field of research that can be substantially expanded. This paper only scratches the tip of the iceberg. The results presented in chapter 7 show its potential, but also its weaknesses. Further research has to be done on improvements to the model's performance and robustness. Furthermore, more complex datasets should be evaluated, as this work suffered from a too small dataset and, thus, too little training time for the model. The original MADRM was trained with 300k pre-training steps and a batch size of 1024, which is not possible for this small setup.

To be honest, a small bug was found in the query generation code at the end of this work, which led to partly noisy query data. This likely has a negative impact on the performance of all trained models.

8.1 Query Dataset

More natural and real-world queries from real users should be collected for the query dataset. A good mix of real-world queries for good semantic and generated ones for diversity is probably best for a reliable dataset. Furthermore, collected queries could be used to create templates for query generation. Additionally, the queries should be translated into multiple languages to train the encoder for better multilingual support.

When using generated queries, it is conceivable that aspects are not only used directly, but also in the form of calculated “virtual” aspects. For example, the aspect “`registration_date`” could also be used as the “age” aspect of a car, which does not exist. So, aspects used to generate queries could be converted to “virtual” aspects that do not exist in the vocabulary, like “age” could be used instead of “`registration_date`”. This is also the advantage of well-labeled real-world queries because they offer more complex expressions and interrelationships in the text than generated queries.

Another point to consider for generated queries is unit conversion. Instead of relying on the default unit or unit of the term only, the generation process could also convert numerical information to different units on a random basis. The vocabulary should contain values in the default units, which will be used to label queries and documents.

All those methods help to build a more diversified query dataset for a more robust MADRM.

8.2 Document Dataset

The document dataset is the bottleneck in this work. Future research has to evaluate the model's performance on a much larger dataset with more heterogeneous data and multilingualism. It is also not clear, whether this study is generalizable to other types of large files or even other JSON structures, as it is concentrated on car data only.

8.3 Model Architecture

To increase the model's robustness against mangling user input, it could be trained on queries with typographical errors or bad expressions. The BERTwiche model (Srivastava & Chiang, 2023) was already used to evaluate noisy BERT inputs. It is made of two additional encoder layers that sandwich the original BERT encoder to minimize the classification error introduced by noisy text and, thus, over-segmentation and sub word replacement by the tokenizer. This adjustment might be useful for the query encoder.

For the document encoder, an improvement for more efficiency would be the introduction of the Longformer model (Beltagy et al., 2020). It would greatly reduce the training time for long documents because the input could be passed to the encoder at once instead of chunk by chunk. The results could then be compared to the chunking approach proposed in this paper to evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of both techniques.

To name a last adjustment, while not a pure architectural one, is better handling of numbers, or rather all continuous values. Studies have shown that NLP models, especially BERT, are not able to capture the numeration and magnitude of numbers sufficiently (Sundararaman et al., 2020; Wallace et al., 2019). The DICE framework (Sundararaman et al., 2020) provides a solution to train NLP models for better number understanding. It also provides a general auxiliary loss for all text models:

$$L_{num} = \left\| \left\| 2 \frac{|x - y|}{|x| + |y|} - \frac{E_x E_y^T}{\|E_x\|_2 \|E_y\|_2} \right\| \right\|_2 \quad (25)$$

In the equation above, x and y represent two random numbers in the batch and E_x, E_y their corresponding embeddings. It simply measures the difference between the normalized distance of the numbers and the cosine similarity of their embeddings. To use it, labels with numbers would be needed. Numbers can also be extracted from the input text. A challenge here is to examine the handling of floating-point or large numbers. They have in common that they use multiple tokens and are thus not represented by a single embedding.

8.4 Training

To further improve the model, the training process could be further optimized. It could use more advanced techniques like hyperparameter tuning or experiment with different warm-up and learning rate schedules. Another common technique is to use k-folds cross validation instead of the train, validate, test split, which could improve the model's performance on unseen data. Furthermore, a loss function specialized to optimize the NDCG value (Qiu et al., 2022) could be used during fine-tuning to better improve the model's ability to rank.

8.5 Similarity Search

It might be worth using the aspect embeddings as a vector set instead of fusing them and doing an ANN search based on vector sets. There are filter techniques for vector sets (Brecheisen, 2007), and additionally, anisotropic quantization could be applied too, mirroring recent research on high-dimensional ANN search.

8.6 Recap

This chapter outlined some potentially valuable improvements for the query and document datasets, the model architecture, as well as for similarity search. The datasets should be larger and more multifaceted. Additionally, the model could be trained on typos or with an auxiliary loss for continuous data. Furthermore, the Longformer could be used as a document encoder instead of BERT. Regarding similarity search, it might be worth to examine efficient similarity search on vector sets using aspect embeddings without fusion.

9 Conclusion

This work dealt with multiple aspect of multi-aspect dense retrieval. It has shown how the proposed model architecture works and that there is much space for improvement. It was tested, whether using the CLS embeddings instead of the “OTHER” aspect is helpful. This could not be reproduced. But it was shown that the model can be further optimized using a special loss for continuous values to predict intervals. Furthermore, chunking was introduced to handle large documents. It was shown, that the model can understand JSON documents and supports multilingualism. Although chunking shows great potential and better document understanding after pre-training, these gains cannot be hold after fine-tuning. This could mean that chunking models need even more training because of their complexity.

All in all, the models presented in this paper are not yet ready for use but offer a foundation for further research. This paper presents the field of MADR from many sides, and provides ideas for improvements as well as insights into the MADRM architecture and its way of working.

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Appendix A The Template Engine

To generate queries, a self-made templating engine is used. This way, multiple different queries can be generated using just one template. It is useful to vary in wording and use different sentence structures to enable a broader understanding of real-world data in the language model. The template engine uses the following patterns to help achieve those benefits:

Placeholder. `{aspect}` — Curly brackets signal a placeholder. They contain an aspect key and are replaced by an aspect term. Example: `{color_out}` might be replaced by “red”.

Pluralized-group. `~{aspect, singular, plural}` — Curly brackets preceded by a tilde take two more parameters than only the aspect name: singular and plural names. The correct name is chosen based on the value of the term used to replace the placeholder. E.g., `~{amount_accidents, accident, accidents}`.

Special values. `*{aspect, dict_name}` — If a star is the preceding character, the name of a predefined dictionary with templates for each term of the aspect is added as a parameter to the placeholder. This is useful if terms only consist of abbreviations and the queries are supposed to contain the correct descriptions. That may be the case for ISO 3166-1 alpha-2 codes for the country aspect: `{country, country_names}`.

If-else group. `?{aspect, target_value, yes, no}` — Beginning with a question mark, placeholders can define a target value, a text for matching terms, and an else case.

List. `#{aspect, count}` — When a hashtag is used before the group, a count can be further specified to pick this amount of items from the aspect terms and list them.

Spans. `</=>{aspect}` — For lower as, greater as, or equal signs, spans are created. For the equal sign, two values are selected that make up a closed interval. Spans are only available in combination with continuous aspects and only used for templates where the whole vocabulary is used as documents do not contain spans themselves. When spans are used, all matching values are labeled automatically.

Variable Appearance. `[x]` — Everything enclosed in square brackets has a 50% chance to appear in the result. For example, `[the]emission` can result in “emission” and “the emission”.

Choice. `(x1|x2[|...])` or `(x1&x2[&...])` — Everything in round brackets is a choice group. Elements are separated either by a “|” or an “&” sign. If “|” is used, one random element is selected to replace the group. If the delimiter is “&” instead, a random permutation with a random length is chosen. This way, `max(.|imum|)` is able to produce “max” “max.” and “maximum”, while `{manufacturer}&{carline}&{model_type}` randomly selects a variable amount from the three placeholders and places them in a random order.

Based on those groups, the templating engine creates a random query for a template and annotates the correct labels on the fly.

Appendix B ChatGPT Prompts

To generate templates using ChatGPT-4 in German language, the following prompts have been used. They were then analyzed and transformed into a template format for the template engine explained in Appendix A to generate multiple queries from one search request provided. The templates were used in German. The English translations are given in brackets behind the respective prompt.

Generate search requests like a car dealer employee:

Du bist ein Mitarbeiter eines Autohändlers und möchtest die Fahrzeugdatenbank durchsuchen. Dafür nutzt du verschiedene detaillierte Angaben zu Fahrzeugen. Für die Suche steht dir ein KI-Assistent zur Verfügung, dem du in deinen Worten in natürlicher Sprache beschreiben kannst, was du suchst. Formuliere dafür 5 verschiedene Suchanfragen.

(You are an employee of a car dealer and want to search the vehicle database. To do this, you use various detailed vehicle details. An AI assistant is available for the search, which you can describe what you are looking for in your own words using natural language. To do this, formulate 5 different search queries.)

Du bist ein Mitarbeiter eines Autohändlers und möchtest die Fahrzeugdatenbank durchsuchen. Dafür nutzt du verschiedene detaillierte Angaben zu Fahrzeugen in verschiedenen Komplexitäten. Für die Suche steht dir ein KI-Assistent zur Verfügung, dem du in deinen Worten in natürlicher Sprache schreiben kannst, was du suchst. Formuliere dafür 10 verschiedene Suchanfragen mit möglichst variablen Worten, um mehrere Nutzergruppen abzubilden. Vermeide dabei Begriffe, die nicht eindeutig sind, wie z.B. "günstig" oder "Familienauto".

(You are an employee of a car dealer and want to search the vehicle database. To do this, you use various detailed information on vehicles in different complexities. For the search, you have an AI assistant at your disposal to which you can write what you are looking for in your own words in natural language. To do this, formulate 10 different search queries with words that are as variable as possible in order to represent several user groups. Avoid terms that are not unique, such as "cheap" or "family car".)

To generate more:

Generiere 10 weitere solcher Anfragen.

(Generate 10 more such requests.)

Make them more complex or less complex:

Nun erhöhe bitte die Komplexität deiner Suchanfragen. Sie dürfen mehr Aspekte eines Fahrzeugs beinhalten und länger sein.

(Now please increase the complexity of your search queries. They may include more aspects of a vehicle and be longer.)

Generiere bitte 15 weitere solcher Anfragen. Nutze diesmal andere Satzanfänge oder auch verkürzte Sätze und Angaben.

(Please generate 15 more such requests. This time, use different sentence beginnings or shortened sentences and details.)

Generiere bitte 10 weitere solcher Anfragen. Nutze diesmal andere Satzanfänge oder auch verkürzte Sätze und Angaben. Verringere außerdem die Komplexität der Anfragen; sie dürfen teilweise auch aus nur einem Wort bestehen.

(Please generate 10 more such requests. This time, use different sentence beginnings or shortened sentences and information. Also reduce the complexity of the queries; some of them may consist of just one word.)

Erhöhe nun leicht die Komplexität.

(Now slightly increase the complexity.)

Appendix C Model Architectures

Figure 17: Model architectures - BiBERT (left), MtBERT (right).

Figure 18: MADR model architecture.

Figure 19: MADRAL model architecture.

Figure 20: MADRAL(N)-CLS model architecture.

Figure 21: CMADRAL model architecture.

Figure 22: BERT-Encoder architecture. Last layer is replaced by aspects layer.

Figure 23: How the AEN works.

Appendix D Document Overfitting and Warm-Up

The following pre-training graphs show experiments with batch sizes and warm-up to prevent document overfitting and a strange behavior of the MLM loss. When one warm-up epoch is used, non-chunked models seem to get directed into a false local minimum, which destroys the document encoder. The MLM loss suddenly rises and gets stuck, as well as the document loss. When using 0.1 warm-up epochs, this does not happen for MADRAL-CLS and MADRALN, but MADRAL gets there besides any efforts to prevent this.

Figure 24: Document encoder overfitting while pre-training MADRAL with batch size 64 for both encoders.

Figure 25: Document encoder not overfitting while pre-training MADARL with batch sizes of 128 for queries and 10 for documents.

Figure 26: MLM loss behavior when pre-training MADRAL.

Figure 27: MLM loss behavior for all non-chunked models with 1 warm-up epoch.

Figure 28: Document loss behavior for all non-chunked models with 1 warm-up epoch.

Figure 29: MLM-loss behavior for all non-chunked models with 0.1 warm-up epoch.

Figure 30: Document loss behavior for all non-chunked models with 0.1 warm-up epochs.

Figure 31: MADRAL-CLS Document pre-training loss with improved batch size and warm-up.

Appendix E Different Values for λ

CMADRALN was fine-tuned with $\lambda=0$ and $\lambda=0.01$ for equation (24). Figure 32 shows that the fine-tuning loss for both variants is nearly equal. In Figure 33, however, you can see that the NDCG of the model with a bit of pre-training loss seems to be more stable and outperforms the variant without pre-training loss. Additionally, it becomes clear in Figure 34 that the learned aspect embeddings are destroyed when no pre-training loss is used. This might work, but it removes the interpretability of the model in terms of explicit aspects.

Figure 32: Fine-tuning loss for model variants with and without using λ .

Figure 33: Fine-tuning NDCG for model variants with and without using λ .

Figure 34: Fine-tuning pre-training loss for model variants with and without using λ .

Lessons Learned

This additional chapter does not add any more scientific information to this thesis but reflects my personal findings in approaching the writing of a paper and the development of neural networks.

Writing a paper. I learned how to structure it and what to include in the separate chapters. I noticed that it is helpful to gather many potential references early to understand the field of study and have a broad overview of related work. This time, many references came gradually when I dove deeper into specific topics. Next time, I will start early with well-founded research before starting the development. Furthermore, it is a good idea to have a rough plan and timetable from the beginning, as I tend to do many side experiments and pursue ideas for improvements. Thus, I forgot about time sometimes and got in a rush at the end of this work.

Dense Retrieval. I highly appreciate the possibility of working on this topic. I enjoyed every second of it, although there were difficulties. For me, it is a fascinating topic with great potential. I began with very basic knowledge about shallow neural networks and learned about all the technologies presented on the previous pages. Transformers, how language models are trained, bi-encoders, ANN, ranking, ranking metrics, and statistical tests—all those things were new to me.

Developing a DNN. Like reference research, which should be done before writing, package research should be done before development. This helps to find useful tools before coming up with a self-made solution for a problem that has long been resolved. For example, I developed a history class to manage metrics, which are reported at every step. I was always frustrated by the limitations of it and had to rework it between runs. Then, I discovered “Weights and Biases”, which is a platform to log metrics to, with real-time visualization, run management, and many more useful features. Unfortunately, I discovered it quite late, but it was still very useful in the end. It can be used to visualize the single losses of the model and find unintended training behavior. But not only research is important for development. Planning the code structure is another essential part I lacked during this work. First, I started with a mess of Jupyter notebooks, which were difficult to overview. Then, I transformed them into classes, which were used with fewer notebooks and cells. That required reloading the notebooks when the code inside the classes changed, which was a very painful process sometimes, with long loading times. Another crucial thing I figured out during the training process is to create checkpoints often, and not only after an epoch (depending on the epoch size). The process crashed several times for different reasons, and it is unpleasant to train from the start again. And, before starting the training, always look at the model code twice. More than once, a run was useless because of undetected bugs.

All in all, I learned a lot. I am glad of the progress I have made and will happily finish this thesis with the following quote:

“Success is stumbling from failure to failure with no loss of enthusiasm.”
(Winston Churchill)

Statutory Declaration

I herewith formally declare that I have written the submitted dissertation independently. I did not use any outside support except for the quoted literature and other sources mentioned in the paper.

Furthermore, I clearly marked and separately listed all the literature and all the other sources which I employed when producing this academic work, either literally or in content.

I am aware that the violation of this regulation will lead to failure of the thesis.

Justin Konratt

Student's name

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Matriculation number

June 10, 2023

Stralsund, date